

Graphical Abstract

A linear SLAM back-end optimization algorithm based on virtual coordinate system and similar triangles

Zhitao Wu, Guangyu Liu

Coarsely estimated trajectory

Accurately estimated trajectory

Highlights

A linear SLAM back-end optimization algorithm based on virtual coordinate system and similar triangles

Zhitao Wu, Guangyu Liu

- Proposes a fully linear 3D SLAM back-end optimization framework
- Introduces a virtual coordinate system for linear pose constraints
- Utilizes gravity-aligned decomposition to enhance stability and efficiency
- Enables unified optimization across LiDAR, IMU, GPS, and camera data
- Achieves robust, scalable, and iteration-free SLAM optimization performance

A linear SLAM back-end optimization algorithm based on virtual coordinate system and similar triangles

Zhitao Wu^{a,1}, Guangyu Liu^{a,*}

^aDepartment of Automation, Hangzhou Dianzi University, Hangzhou, 310018, Zhejiang, China

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

SLAM, Back-end optimization, Linear equations, Outlier removal.

ABSTRACT

Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) is a fundamental problem in robotics and autonomous systems. Traditional SLAM back-end optimization methods, such as Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and graph-based nonlinear optimization, often rely on iterative procedures and local linearization, which limit their robustness and computational efficiency in large-scale and highly nonlinear environments. To address these limitations, this paper proposes a novel SLAM back-end optimization algorithm based entirely on linear equations in three-dimensional space. The method introduces a virtual coordinate system for each node and formulates pose transformations as a system of linear constraints using the geometric similarity of spatial triangles and tetrahedra. By leveraging the gravity direction measured by the IMU, the algorithm decouples the horizontal and vertical components of motion, enabling efficient projection of spatial relationships onto the ground plane. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm supports various sensors, including LiDAR, IMU, and GPS, and incorporates a robust outlier removal mechanism. Extensive numerical experiments demonstrate that the proposed algorithm achieves accuracy comparable to state-of-the-art nonlinear optimization methods while significantly reducing computation time, offering a scalable and robust solution for real-time SLAM applications.

1. Introduction

In simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) systems, back-end optimization plays a critical role in determining the geometric consistency and accuracy of the overall system. The mainstream approaches to back-end optimization can be broadly categorized into two types: the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF)-based filtering methods and the graph optimization methods based on batch nonlinear optimization.

EKF-SLAM is one of the earliest proposed back-end optimization methods. Its fundamental concept involves modeling the entire system state as a high-dimensional Gaussian distribution, and recursively estimating the joint state of the robot pose and map landmarks through a Gaussian prediction-update mechanism Bailey, Nieto, Guivant, Stevens and Nebot (2006). The primary advantage of the EKF lies in its real-time performance, allowing for high-frequency state updates. However, due to its inherent first-order linearization of nonlinear processes, EKF-SLAM tends to suffer from inconsistency during long-term operation, particularly in scenarios involving severe nonlinearity or high-dimensional state spaces. To address these issues, various improvements have been proposed, such as Robocentric-EKF Martinez-Cantin and Castellanos (2006), Divide & Conquer SLAM Paz, Tardós and Neira (2008), and the Invariant EKF (RI-EKF) Zhang, Wu, Song, Huang and Dissanayake (2017), aiming to mitigate linearization errors and enhance the consistency of the EKF framework.

The graph optimization approach formulates the SLAM problem as a nonlinear least-squares optimization, in which the variables consist of a sequence of robot poses and map

points, and the constraints are derived from sensor observations Grisetti, Kümmerle, Stachniss and Burgard (2010). In contrast to the EKF, graph optimization does not rely on Bayesian recursion; instead, it minimizes the error terms of the entire graph structure in a single optimization process. This method offers improved accuracy and robustness, particularly in nonlinear modeling and large-scale environments. Representative implementations include g2o Koenig, Grisetti, Kümmerle, Burgard, Limketkai and Vincent (2010) and Ceres Solver. In recent years, several approaches have been proposed based on graph optimization, such as CPL-SLAM Fan, Wang, Rubenstein and Murphey (2020), Sparse PGO Bai, Vidal-Calleja and Grisetti (2021), CycleSpace PGO Carlone, Calafiore, Tommolillo and Dellaert (2016), and Distributed PGO Tian, Khosoussi, Rosen and How (2021), which enhance computational efficiency, stability, and scalability.

Although both the EKF and graph-based optimization exhibit distinct advantages in terms of real-time performance and accuracy, respectively, these two categories of methods commonly rely on local linearization. Specifically, they approximate nonlinear systems by employing Taylor expansion to obtain locally linear models. This inherent reliance on local linearization fundamentally constrains the system's stability when confronted with severe nonlinearities, scale drift, or mismatched observations. In recent years, various approaches have been proposed to enhance the computational efficiency and robustness of SLAM back-end optimization by reformulating the SLAM problem into a linear form. Most of these methods construct SLAM models that can be directly solved using linear equations by means of state variable decoupling, subgraph stitching, or structural assumptions such as the Manhattan world or Atlanta world.

 jkk@example.in (G. Liu)
ORCID(s):

The Linear SLAM method was proposed by Zhao et al., in which the SLAM problem is transformed into a series of linear least-squares problems through submap stitching Zhao, Huang and Dissanayake (2013). This approach is applicable to both feature-based and pose graph-based SLAM paradigms, and does not require initial values or covariance assumptions. Building upon this framework, Cheng et al. introduced the Toward Robust Linear SLAM method, incorporating delayed optimization and an EM-based weighting mechanism to robustly handle erroneous loop closures Cheng, Jiang, Zhang and Kim (2014). In structured environments, Joo et al. employed the Manhattan and Atlanta world assumptions to reformulate the RGB-D SLAM problem as a linear Bayesian filtering problem Joo, Kim, Hebert, Kweon and Kim (2022); Joo, Oh, Rameau, Bazin and Kweon (2020). By modeling the structural characteristics of the scene, their method effectively decouples rotation and translation, enhances linearity, and reduces reliance on nonlinear optimization.

To avoid the iterative processes inherent in traditional methods, several studies have proposed various forms of closed-form solutions. Dubbelman et al. introduced the Closed-form Pose-chain SLAM, which achieves accuracy comparable to iterative methods while operating at significantly higher speeds — up to an order of magnitude faster Dubbelman and Browning (2013, 2015). Lee et al. proposed a non-iterative graph optimization method wherein rotation and translation components of the pose graph are separately solved using linear least squares jae Lee, moon Jang and il Dan Cho (2014). Martinelli presented a comprehensive set of closed-form solutions for visual-inertial systems, enabling the estimation of orientation, velocity, scale, and IMU biases without requiring any initial values Martinelli (2012). The initialization problem in Pose Graph Optimization (PGO) has a critical impact on the final results. Nasiri et al. proposed a novel initialization approach based on linear least squares, which outperforms existing methods in high-noise scenarios Nasiri, Moradi and Hosseini (2018). Dellaert et al. achieved sparse linear solutions to the SLAM back-end problem through variable separation techniques Khosoussi, Huang and Dissanayake (2016).

Liu et al. reformulated the 2D Pose SLAM problem as a Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Program (QCQP) and further relaxed it into a Semidefinite Program (SDP), thereby obtaining an approximation of the globally optimal solution Liu, Huang, Dissanayake and Wang (2012). Briaies et al. proposed a fast optimality verification method based on certifiable theory, which significantly improved the robustness of graph optimization solutions Briaies and Gonzalez-Jimenez (2016). Khosoussi et al. identified a separable linear structure inherent in SLAM problems and introduced the Sparse Separable SLAM approach, which decomposes the nonlinear problem into alternating solutions of a linear kernel and a nonlinear core Jian, Balcan and Dellaert (2011). Jiang et al. employed variational Bayesian inference and achieved linear complexity SLAM inference through mean-field approximation Jiang, Hoy, Yu and Dauwels (2017). In

extended scenarios such as RFID, visual-inertial navigation, and point cloud registration, SLAM or registration problems have also been reformulated as linear equation solving. For instance, Tzitzis et al. reconstructed the RFID localization problem as a linear least squares problem Tzitzis, Malama, Drakaki, Bletsas, Yioultis and Dimitriou (2022), while Pavan et al. proposed a closed-form solution for global registration of laser point clouds, thereby avoiding the iterative procedure required in traditional registration methods Pavan and dos Santos (2017).

In summary, although numerous studies have attempted to incorporate linear methods into SLAM, most of these approaches rely on specific assumptions — such as the Manhattan world, known structures, local submaps, or known rotations — or apply linear solvers only to certain sub-modules, such as initialization or registration. In response to these limitations, this study proposes a SLAM back-end optimization algorithm constructed entirely based on linear equations.

The key contributions and innovations of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- **Linear formulation of the SLAM back-end problem.** Unlike conventional nonlinear optimization or EKF-based methods that rely on iterative linearization, this work proposes a completely linear equation-based SLAM back-end optimization framework in three-dimensional space. All pose constraints are represented by linear relationships derived from geometric similarity among spatial triangles and tetrahedra, eliminating the need for iterative nonlinear solvers.
- **Introduction of a virtual coordinate system.** A virtual coordinate system is defined for each node, enabling pose transformations to be reformulated as linear constraints among virtual nodes. This mechanism effectively preserves the geometric structure while simplifying the representation of spatial relationships in the global coordinate frame.
- **Gravity-aligned decomposition of spatial relationships.** By utilizing IMU-measured gravity direction, the algorithm performs a decoupled representation of horizontal and vertical components of motion, thereby projecting spatial constraints onto the ground plane and significantly improving computational efficiency and numerical stability.
- **Unified multi-sensor compatibility.** The proposed formulation supports data from various sensors — including LiDAR, IMU, GPS, and cameras — by converting all types of relative pose transformations into the same linear equation framework, achieving unified and consistent optimization across modalities.
- **Robust and scalable optimization without iteration.** The linear system design inherently avoids the

convergence issues of nonlinear optimization and ensures high computational efficiency, robustness to initialization errors, and excellent scalability in large-scale environments. Additionally, a robust outlier removal mechanism is integrated to suppress the influence of erroneous edge measurements and enhance mapping consistency.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Sec. 2 defines the problem and establishes the mathematical formulation used in our approach. Sec. 3 presents the proposed method in detail, including the algorithmic design and implementation details. Sec. 4 provides a theoretical analysis of the computational complexity of the proposed method. Sec. 5 reports extensive experimental results and comparisons to verify the effectiveness and efficiency of our approach. Finally, Sec. 6 concludes the paper and discusses possible directions for future work.

2. Problem formulation

We formulate the back-end of SLAM as a pose graph optimization problem. Nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$ are used to represent keyframes, each associated with a local coordinate frame Σ_i . Each node has an unknown rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i \in \text{SO}(3)$ that relates the local frame Σ_i to the global coordinate frame Σ_g . The robot pose can then be represented as

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_i & \mathbf{t}_i \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \text{SE}(3), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{t}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position of the robot in 3D space.

Each edge encodes a spatial constraint between two poses $(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$ estimated from sensor observations or loop closures. Given the set of all constraints $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \text{SE}(3), i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$. A directed graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ can then be defined, in which \mathcal{V} represents the set of all nodes (keyframes), and \mathcal{E} represents the set of all pose transformations. The objective is to estimate all robot poses $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}$ by minimizing the accumulated residual errors induced by these constraints.

$$\min_{\{\mathbf{x}_i\}} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}} \|r_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{T}_{ij})\|_{\Sigma_{ij}^{-1}}^2, \quad (2)$$

where $r_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{T}_{ij}) = \log(\mathbf{T}_{ij}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_i^{-1} \mathbf{x}_j))$ denotes the residual error under measurement \mathbf{T}_{ij} , and Σ_{ij} the measurement covariance.

It is assumed that all measurement data are independent, with the majority affected by Gaussian-distributed noise and a small portion containing outlier noise. Existing graph optimization algorithms generally require iterative procedures to minimize nonlinear functions, which leads to high computational complexity. In this study, a SLAM back-end optimization framework based solely on linear equations is proposed. Since the algorithm eliminates the need for iterative computation, it exhibits lower computational cost

and improved interpretability. Table 1 provides a brief definition of the symbols used in this paper, while the complete definitions are presented in the corresponding sections.

3. Proposed Method

3.1. Algorithm overview

In this study, a back-end optimization algorithm based on linear equations is proposed, and its system framework is illustrated in Fig. 1. The input data of the algorithm consist of GPS sensor latitude and longitude measurements, as well as the pose transformation data from non-GPS sensors, denoted as $\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \text{SE}(3)$. The output of the algorithm corresponds to the optimized poses of each node, represented as $\mathbf{x}_i \in \text{SE}(3)$.

The input data from non-GPS sensors are the pose transformations \mathbf{T}_{ij} , which are first processed in the outlier removal module to eliminate outliers. The details of this module are presented in Sec. 3.6. The remaining pose transformations \mathbf{T}_{ij} are subsequently converted into linear equations $\mathbf{A}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}^{\text{xy}}$, $\mathbf{A}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z = \mathbf{b}^z$, $\mathbf{C}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{D}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}}$, $\mathbf{C}^z \mathbf{p}^z = \mathbf{D}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z$, as described in Secs. 3.2 and 3.3.

The latitude and longitude data obtained from the GPS sensor are converted into a linear equation $\mathbf{E}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = 0$, the details of which are presented in Sec. 3.4. Subsequently, the linear equation derived from non-GPS sensor data, and the linear equation $\mathbf{E}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = 0$, derived from GPS data, are both utilized to compute the map scale ρ and the node coordinates \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} , \mathbf{p}_v^z , \mathbf{p}^{xy} , \mathbf{p}^z , as described in Sec. 3.5. The computation of the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i for the local coordinate system of each node is then performed, as detailed in Sec. 3.7. After obtaining the three-dimensional coordinates \mathbf{t}_i and the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i for each node, the pose of each node is represented as $\mathbf{x}_i = [\mathbf{R}_i, \mathbf{t}_i; 1, 0]$.

The detailed procedures of this algorithm are described in Secs. 3.2–3.7.

3.2. Representation of geometric shapes using linear equations

3.2.1. Representation of a triangle using linear equations

The shape of an arbitrary triangle on the plane is represented using linear equations. As illustrated in Fig. 2, let the coordinates of the three vertices of triangle \triangle_{ijk} on the plane be $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Given that the length of edge \overline{ij} is ρ_{ij} , the length of edge \overline{ik} is ρ_{ik} , and the angle \angle_{jik} is θ_{jik} , these three constraints define a congruent triangle. In order to express pose constraints between nodes using linear equations, the congruence constraint is relaxed to a similarity constraint, namely $\rho_{jik} = \rho_{ik}/\rho_{ij}, \theta_{jik}$. This relaxation ensures that the shape of triangle \triangle_{ijk} is preserved, although the triangle as a whole may undergo scaling. Under this formulation, the set of similarity constraints can be represented using the linear systems given in Eqs. (3) and (4).

$$\mathbf{p}_k - \mathbf{p}_i = \rho_{jik} \mathbf{R}_{jik} (\mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_i), \quad (3)$$

Symbol	Definition
i, i_x, i_y, i_z	The origin and the unit points along the x-, y-, and z-axes, respectively, of the local coordinate system Σ_i . ^a
j, j_x, j_y, j_z	The origin and the unit points along the x-, y-, and z-axes, respectively, of the local coordinate system Σ_j . ^a
$P_i, P_{i_x}, P_{i_y}, P_{i_z}$	Global coordinates of points i, i_x, i_y, i_z . ^a
$P_i^{xy}, P_{i_x}^{xy}, P_{i_y}^{xy}, P_{i_z}^{xy}$	The x- and y-axis components of the global coordinates of nodes i, i_x, i_y, i_z . ^a
$z_i, z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}$	The z-axis components of the global coordinates of nodes i, i_x, i_y, i_z . ^a
$P_j, P_{j_x}, P_{j_y}, P_{j_z}$	Global coordinates of points j, j_x, j_y, j_z . ^a
$P_j^{xy}, P_{j_x}^{xy}, P_{j_y}^{xy}, P_{j_z}^{xy}$	The x- and y-axis components of the global coordinates of nodes j, j_x, j_y, j_z . ^a
$z_j, z_{j_x}, z_{j_y}, z_{j_z}$	The z-axis components of the global coordinates of nodes j, j_x, j_y, j_z . ^a
p, p^{xy}, p^z	The vector composed of all virtual nodes, the vector containing the x- and y-axis components, and the vector containing the z-axis components, respectively. ^a
p_v, p_v^{xy}, p_v^z	The vector composed of all nodes, the vector containing the x- and y-axis components, and the vector containing the z-axis components, respectively. ^a
p_{sub}^{xy}	Vector obtained from p^{xy} by removing nodes $1, 1_x, 1_y, 1_z$. ^b
p_{sub}^z	Vector obtained from p^z by removing nodes $1, 1_x, 1_y, 1_z$. ^b
p_{acc}^{xy}	Combined vector defined as $p_{acc}^{xy} = [p^{xyT}, p_v^{xyT}]^T$. ^b
$p_{sub,acc}^{xy}$	Vector obtained from p_{acc}^{xy} by removing nodes $1, 1_x, 1_y, 1_z$. ^b

Table 1
Summary of Symbol Definitions

[a] Full definition in Sec. 3.3.1. [b] Full definition in Sec. 3.5.1.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the algorithm

$$\mathbf{R}_{jik} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_{jik} & -\sin \theta_{jik} \\ \sin \theta_{jik} & \cos \theta_{jik} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where p_i, p_j , and p_k denote the coordinates of nodes i, j , and k , respectively, and are the variables to be constrained. The term $\mathbf{R}_{jik}(p_j - p_i)$ represents the vector $\vec{i_j}$ rotated by the angle θ_{jik} , resulting in a vector aligned in the same direction as vector $\vec{i_k}$. Furthermore, a proportional relationship exists between $\mathbf{R}_{jik}(p_j - p_i)$ and vector $\vec{i_k}$, defined by $\rho = \rho_{ik}/\rho_{ij}$. Both ρ and the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_{jik} can be computed using the pose transformations T_{ji} and T_{ik} , which are known constants.

In Lin, Fu and Diao (2015), an equivalent form of the above equations is presented using complex linear equations. In that work, a graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ is employed to represent all points in the plane and the relationships among distinct points. Let the complex coordinate of node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ be denoted as $p_i^c = x_i + y_i i \in \mathbb{C}$, where x_i and y_i represent the x- and y-components of node i 's position, respectively. Similarly, the complex coordinate of node $j \in \mathcal{V}$ is defined as $p_j^c =$

$x_j + y_j i \in \mathbb{C}$, with x_j and y_j corresponding to the x- and y-components of node j 's position. The complex coordinate of node $k \in \mathcal{V}$ is given by $p_k^c = x_k + y_k i \in \mathbb{C}$, where x_k and y_k denote the x- and y-components of node k 's position. At this point, the complex coordinates p_i^c, p_j^c , and p_k^c are considered as variables to be constrained in the equations. Accordingly, the linear systems represented by Eqs. (3) and (4) can be reformulated using the complex linear equations given in Eqs. (5) and (6).

$$p_k^c - p_i^c = \omega_{jik}(p_j^c - p_i^c), \quad (5)$$

$$\omega_{jik} = \rho_{jik} e^{i\theta_{jik}}. \quad (6)$$

The equivalence between the linear equations. (3), (4) and the complex linear equations (5), (6) is demonstrated. As shown in Eq. (7), let $p_{ki}^c \in \mathbb{C}$ denote the complex coordinate representation of vector $\vec{i_k}$, and let θ_{ki} represent the angle of vector $\vec{i_k}$. Similarly, as presented in Eq. (8), let $p_{ji}^c \in \mathbb{C}$

denote the complex coordinate representation of vector \vec{ij} , and let θ_{ji} represent the angle of vector \vec{ij} .

$$p_{ki}^c = p_k^c - p_i^c = \rho_{ki} e^{i\theta_{ki}}, \quad (7)$$

$$p_{ji}^c = p_j^c - p_i^c = \rho_{ji} e^{i\theta_{ji}}. \quad (8)$$

The expressions p_{ki}^c and p_{ji}^c are substituted for p_k^c, p_i^c , and p_j^c in Eq. (3), yielding Eq. (9).

$$\rho_{ki} e^{i\theta_{ki}} = \omega_{jik} \rho_{ji} e^{i\theta_{ji}}. \quad (9)$$

Subsequently, the parameter ω_{jik} from Eq. (4) is substituted into Eq. (8), resulting in Eq. (10).

$$\rho_{ki} e^{i\theta_{ki}} = \rho_{jik} \rho_{ji} e^{i(\theta_{ji} + \theta_{jik})}. \quad (10)$$

As shown in Eq. (11), Eq. (10) can be reformulated into constraints on the magnitude component and the angular component.

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{jik} = \frac{\rho_{ik}}{\rho_{ij}} \\ \theta_{ji} + \theta_{jik} = \theta_{ki} \end{cases}. \quad (11)$$

These constraints are identical to the similarity triangle constraints involving nodes i, j , and k . Accordingly, the aforementioned linear equations in the complex domain can equivalently represent the shape constraint of triangle $\triangle jik$. Both the linear equations in the real domain and those in the complex domain provide equivalent formulations of the constraint for triangle $\triangle jik$. In the remainder of the text, the linear equations in the complex domain will be adopted to represent the pose constraints among the three nodes, as they offer a more concise representation, requiring only a single equation. The coordinate of an arbitrary node i is thus represented in the complex domain as $p_i^c = x_i + y_i i \in \mathbb{C}$.

The degenerate case of the equation is analyzed when any two nodes of the triangle $\triangle jik$ coincide. Suppose nodes i and k coincide; in this case, $\rho_{ik} = 0$, and $\rho_{jik} = \rho_{ik}/\rho_{ij} = 0$. Consequently, the parameter $\omega_{jik} = \rho_{jik} e^{i\theta_{jik}} = 0$. The corresponding complex linear equation is given in Eq. (12).

$$p_k^c - p_i^c = 0(p_j^c - p_i^c). \quad (12)$$

When node i coincides with node k , the equation degenerates into $p_i^c = p_k^c$. Similarly, if node i coincides with node j , the equation reduces to $p_i^c = p_j^c$. In the case where node j coincides with node k , the equation becomes $p_j^c = p_k^c$. If nodes i, j , and k coincide, the equation simplifies to $p_i^c = p_j^c = p_k^c$. Eqs (13) and (14) represent the degenerate forms of the equation under these node coincidence conditions.

$$\begin{cases} p_i^c = p_j^c, & \text{if } \rho_{ij} < \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ p_i^c = p_k^c, & \text{if } \rho_{ik} < \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ p_j^c = p_k^c, & \text{if } \rho_{jk} < \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

$$p_i^c = p_j^c = p_k^c, & \text{if any two of } \rho_{ij}, \rho_{ik}, \rho_{jk} \text{ are less than } \epsilon_{\text{thres}}, \quad (14)$$

where ϵ_{thres} represents the threshold used to determine whether two nodes are considered coincident.

Subsequently, a specific condition for a localizability problem is introduced. In triangle $\triangle jik$, if the coordinates of nodes i and k are known, and the coordinates of node j are to be computed using a linear equation, the condition under which node j is localizable is as follows: if nodes i and k are not coincident, then node j is localizable. Conversely, if nodes i and k are coincident, the linear equation degenerates to $p_i^c = p_k^c$; this equation is independent of the coordinates of node j , and therefore the coordinates of node j cannot be computed using the linear equation. The same conclusion can also be drawn from a geometric perspective: if nodes i and k are coincident, the known values of ρ_{ij} and ρ_{kj} are insufficient to uniquely determine the coordinates of node j . In this case, node j lies on a circle.

3.2.2. Representation of a spatial triangle using linear equations

In three-dimensional space, four nodes i, j, k, l can form multiple triangles, such as $\triangle ijl$, $\triangle ikl$, and $\triangle jik$. If these nodes lie on the same plane, the shape of each triangle can be represented using the linear equations introduced in the previous section. However, if the nodes are not coplanar, the following method can be employed to construct the corresponding linear equations. This approach utilizes the gravity direction provided by the IMU sensor to project the constraints of similar triangles in space onto the ground plane.

In the following, a linear equation representation of a triangle $\triangle jik$ located in space is discussed. As illustrated in Fig. 3, let the coordinates of the three vertices of triangle $\triangle jik$ in the global coordinate system Σ_g (in which the z -axis is oriented opposite to the direction of gravity) be denoted by $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$, as shown in Eq. (15). These coordinates serve as the variables constrained by the linear system.

$$\mathbf{p}_i = \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_j = \begin{bmatrix} x_j \\ y_j \\ z_j \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_k = \begin{bmatrix} x_k \\ y_k \\ z_k \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

The relative position of node j is measured in the local coordinate frame Σ_i , centered at node i , and is denoted as $\mathbf{p}_j^r = [x_{ij}^r, y_{ij}^r, z_{ij}^r]^T$. Similarly, the relative position of node k in the local coordinate frame Σ_i is given by $\mathbf{p}_k^r = [x_{ik}^r, y_{ik}^r, z_{ik}^r]^T$. An unknown rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$

exists between the local coordinate frame Σ_i and the global coordinate frame Σ_g .

The gravity direction obtained from the IMU sensor is utilized to rectify the local coordinate system Σ_i , resulting in a new local coordinate system Σ_{iz} in which the z -axis is aligned opposite to the direction of gravity (this is achieved using a rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$). The method for computing the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$ is presented below. In the local coordinate system Σ_i , the gravity direction measured by the IMU is denoted as $\mathbf{g}_{\text{ori}} = [x_g, y_g, z_g]^T$. In this work, the gravity direction \mathbf{g}_{ori} is directly obtained from the IMU measurements. In practical applications, a more accurate estimate of the gravity direction can also be obtained by incorporating a motion model of the robot and the known magnitude of gravitational acceleration, and applying estimation techniques such as the Kalman filter.

The global coordinate system is defined such that its z -axis is oriented opposite to the direction of gravity. For convenience, the variable \mathbf{g}_{inv} is introduced to represent this direction, defined as $\mathbf{g}_{\text{inv}} = -\mathbf{g}_{\text{ori}} = [-x_g, -y_g, -z_g]^T$. Furthermore, it is assumed that the z -axis of the relative position sensing module on the sensor node is aligned with the z -axis of the IMU, denoted as $\mathbf{z} = [0, 0, 1]^T$.

It is necessary to rotate the local coordinate system Σ_i such that the z -axis of the resulting coordinate system Σ_{iz} is aligned in the direction opposite to gravity. Specifically, this involves rotating Σ_i around the normal vector of the plane defined by three points: the IMU's z -axis, node i , and the inverse gravity direction \mathbf{g}_{inv} (denoted as vector $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), by an angle $\alpha \in (-\pi, \pi]$ formed by these three points. In the local coordinate system Σ_i , the IMU's z -axis and the inverse gravity direction are represented by Eqs (16) and (17), respectively.

$$\mathbf{z} = [0, 0, 1]^T, \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_{\text{inv}} = [-x_g, -y_g, -z_g]^T. \quad (17)$$

The normal vector \mathbf{n} can thus be calculated using the vector cross product, as shown in Eq. (18).

$$\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{g}_{\text{inv}} = [y_g, -x_g, 0]^T. \quad (18)$$

As indicated in Eqs. (19) and (20), the rotation angle α can be determined using the dot product.

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \alpha &= \frac{\mathbf{z} \cdot \mathbf{g}_{\text{inv}}}{\|\mathbf{z}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{g}_{\text{inv}}\|}, \\ &= -\frac{z_g}{\sqrt{x_g^2 + y_g^2 + z_g^2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\alpha = \arccos \left(\frac{-z_g}{\sqrt{x_g^2 + y_g^2 + z_g^2}} \right). \quad (20)$$

Accordingly, the rotation vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is expressed as in Eq. (21).

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v} &= \alpha \frac{\mathbf{n}}{\|\mathbf{n}\|}, \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{x_g^2 + y_g^2}} \begin{bmatrix} y_g \\ -x_g \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

After the rotation vector \mathbf{v} is computed, the Rodrigues formula can be employed to convert it into the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$, as shown in Eqs. (22) and (23).

$$\mathbf{v} = \theta \mathbf{u}, \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}} = \mathbf{I} + \sin \theta [\mathbf{u}]_{\times} + (1 - \cos \theta) [\mathbf{u}]_{\times}^2. \quad (23)$$

It should be noted that the rotation of the coordinate system is opposite to the rotation of the observations within the coordinate system. The relative position of node j in the corrected local coordinate system Σ_{iz} is given by Eq. (24).

$$\mathbf{p}_j^{\text{cor}} = (\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x_{ij}^r \\ y_{ij}^r \\ z_{ij}^r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ij}^{\text{cor}} \\ y_{ij}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{ij}^{\text{cor}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

Similarly, the relative position of node k in the corrected local coordinate system Σ_{iz} is expressed in Eq. (25).

$$\mathbf{p}_k^{\text{cor}} = (\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x_{ik}^r \\ y_{ik}^r \\ z_{ik}^r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ik}^{\text{cor}} \\ y_{ik}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{ik}^{\text{cor}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

The corrected relative positions $\mathbf{p}_j^{\text{cor}}, \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{cor}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are projected onto the ground plane, and the projected coordinates are given by Eq. (26).

$$\mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ij}^{\text{cor}} \\ y_{ij}^{\text{cor}} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ik}^{\text{cor}} \\ y_{ik}^{\text{cor}} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_i^{\text{proj}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

In order to represent the relationship among the projected coordinates of vertices i, j , and k on the ground plane using complex linear equations, the x - y components of the node coordinates $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_k$ in Eq. (15) are expressed in complex form, as shown in Eq. (27). Accordingly, the complex coordinates $p_i^{\text{xy}}, p_j^{\text{xy}}, p_k^{\text{xy}}$ serve as the variables to be constrained in the linear equations.

$$\begin{cases} p_i^{\text{xy}} = x_i + y_i i \in \mathbb{C} \\ p_j^{\text{xy}} = x_j + y_j i \in \mathbb{C} \\ p_k^{\text{xy}} = x_k + y_k i \in \mathbb{C} \end{cases}. \quad (27)$$

The projected coordinates of the three vertices i , j , and k of the spatial triangle $\triangle ijk$ onto the horizontal plane, denoted as $p_i^{xy}, p_j^{xy}, p_k^{xy}$, can be expressed using the linear equations provided in Eqs. (28) and (29).

$$p_k^{xy} - p_i^{xy} = \omega_{jik}^{xy} (p_j^{xy} - p_i^{xy}), \quad (28)$$

$$\omega_{jik}^{xy} = \rho_{jik}^{xy} e^{i\theta_{jik}^{xy}}, \quad (29)$$

where the parameter ρ_{jik} is calculated according to Eqs. (30), (31), and (32).

$$\rho_{jik}^{xy} = \frac{\rho_{ik}^{xy}}{\rho_{ij}^{xy}}, \quad (30)$$

$$\rho_{ij}^{xy} = \left\| \mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} - \mathbf{p}_i^{\text{proj}} \right\|, \quad (31)$$

$$\rho_{ik}^{xy} = \left\| \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}} - \mathbf{p}_i^{\text{proj}} \right\|, \quad (32)$$

where the angle θ_{jik}^{xy} is determined as described in Eqs. (33) and (34).

$$\cos \theta_{jik}^{xy} = \frac{\mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}}}{\left\| \mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} \right\| \left\| \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}} \right\|}, \quad (33)$$

$$\theta_{jik}^{xy} = \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}}}{\left\| \mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} \right\| \left\| \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}} \right\|} \right). \quad (34)$$

Subsequently, the linear equations corresponding to the vertical components of the three vertices i, j, k of triangle $\triangle ijk$ are discussed. In Eq. (15), the z -axis components of nodes $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j$, and \mathbf{p}_k are denoted as z_i, z_j , and z_k , respectively. The corrected local coordinate system Σ_{iz} shares the same z -axis direction as the global coordinate system Σ_g , both oriented vertically. In Eq. (24), the relative vertical distance between node i and node j in the local coordinate system Σ_{iz} is given by z_{ij}^{cor} . Similarly, in Eq. (25), the relative vertical distance between node i and node k in Σ_{iz} is denoted as z_{ik}^{cor} . Based on these, the vertical constraint equation in Eq. (35) can be derived.

$$\begin{cases} z_j - z_i = z_{ij}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_k - z_i = z_{ik}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases}. \quad (35)$$

Therefore, for the spatial triangle $\triangle ijk$, the spatial relationship among nodes i, j , and k in the global coordinate system Σ_g can be represented by three linear equations.

Geometrically, these three linear equations impose the following constraints on $\triangle ijk$: first, the projections of the equations onto the horizontal plane ensure that nodes i, j , and k form a similar triangle in the x - y plane, preserving the shape but allowing for uniform scaling. The shape of the triangle formed by nodes i, j , and k in the x - y plane is thus fixed, while its size may vary. Subsequently, the linear equation in the vertical direction constrains the relative vertical distances among nodes i, j , and k . As a result, the spatial triangle $\triangle ijk$ cannot rotate about the x -axis or y -axis without altering the relative vertical distances. Hence, these three equations collectively determine both the configuration of nodes i, j , and k along the vertical direction and the geometric shape in the x - y plane.

The degeneration of the linear equations projected onto the ground plane for nodes i, j , and k is discussed below. The projections of nodes i, j , and k onto the ground plane are denoted as $p_i^{xy}, p_j^{xy}, p_k^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$. If any two of these planar coordinates coincide, the corresponding variation in the linear equations is described by Eqs. (36), (37), and (38).

$$\begin{cases} p_i^{xy} = p_j^{xy}, & \text{if } \rho_{ij}^{xy} < \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ p_i^{xy} = p_k^{xy}, & \text{if } \rho_{ik}^{xy} < \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ p_j^{xy} = p_k^{xy}, & \text{if } \rho_{jk}^{xy} < \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \end{cases}. \quad (36)$$

$$p_i^{xy} = p_j^{xy} = p_k^{xy}, \text{ if any two of } \rho_{ij}^{xy}, \rho_{ik}^{xy}, \rho_{jk}^{xy} \text{ are less than } \epsilon_{\text{thres}}. \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{ij}^{xy} = \left\| \mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} - \mathbf{p}_i^{\text{proj}} \right\| \\ \rho_{ik}^{xy} = \left\| \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}} - \mathbf{p}_i^{\text{proj}} \right\| \\ \rho_{jk}^{xy} = \left\| \mathbf{p}_k^{\text{proj}} - \mathbf{p}_j^{\text{proj}} \right\| \end{cases}, \quad (38)$$

where $\rho_{ij}^{xy} \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the distance between the ground plane coordinates $p_i^{\text{proj}} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $p_j^{\text{proj}} \in \mathbb{R}^2$; $\rho_{ik}^{xy} \in \mathbb{R}$ represents the distance between $p_i^{\text{proj}} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $p_k^{\text{proj}} \in \mathbb{R}^2$; and $\rho_{jk}^{xy} \in \mathbb{R}$ corresponds to the distance between $p_j^{\text{proj}} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $p_k^{\text{proj}} \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

A specific condition for the localizability problem is presented as follows. In a three-dimensional triangle $\triangle ijk$, given the ground-plane coordinates of nodes i and k , denoted as p_i^{xy} and p_k^{xy} respectively, the ground-plane coordinates of node j , p_j^{xy} , are to be computed using a linear equation. The condition under which node j is localizable on the ground plane is as follows: if nodes i and k are not coincident and do not lie on the same vertical line, then the coordinates of node j can be determined on the ground plane. Conversely, if nodes i and k are coincident, or if nodes i and k lie on the same vertical line, the corresponding linear equation degenerates to $p_i^{xy} = p_k^{xy}$. In such cases, the linear equation

is independent of the ground-plane coordinates of node j , p_j^{xy} , and thus these coordinates cannot be computed using the linear equation.

There is no specific constraint on determining the vertical coordinate z_j of node j , as either one of the equations in Eq. (35) is sufficient to compute z_j , regardless of whether nodes i and k coincide or lie on the same vertical line.

Therefore, for the triangle $\triangle ijk$ in three-dimensional space, given the coordinates of node i , $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and node k , $p_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$, the coordinate p_j of node j can be determined provided that nodes i and k are not coincident and do not lie on the same vertical line.

3.2.3. Representation of a tetrahedron using linear equations

In this section, the shape of an arbitrary tetrahedron in space is represented using linear equations. As illustrated in Fig. 4, each tetrahedron consists of four triangular faces; if the shapes of any three of these faces are determined, the overall shape of the tetrahedron is also uniquely determined. To express the constraints between nodes using linear equations, the similarity conditions of triangles are employed to constrain each individual triangle. For instance, for the triangle $\triangle ijk$, the similarity constraint is given by $\rho_{jik} = \rho_{ik}/\rho_{ij}, \theta_{jik}$.

For the tetrahedron $ijkl$, if the similarity constraints for any three of its triangular faces are known, then the shape of the entire tetrahedron (up to scale) is determined. Let the similarity constraints for triangles $\triangle ijl$, $\triangle ikl$, and $\triangle jkl$ be as defined in Eq. (39).

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{ilj} = \rho_{lj}/\rho_{li}, \theta_{ilj} \\ \rho_{ilk} = \rho_{lk}/\rho_{li}, \theta_{ilk} \\ \rho_{jlk} = \rho_{lk}/\rho_{lj}, \theta_{jlk} \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

For each of the aforementioned similar triangle constraints, a linear equation of the triangle in 3D space can be employed for representation. Let the coordinates of nodes i, j, k, l in the global coordinate system Σ_g be denoted as $p_i, p_j, p_k, p_l \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The components of nodes i, j, k, l on the x - y plane are represented by $p_i^{xy}, p_j^{xy}, p_k^{xy}, p_l^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$, which can be expressed using the components of p_i, p_j, p_z, p_l . The components of nodes i, j, k, l along the z -axis are denoted as $z_i, z_j, z_k, z_l \in \mathbb{R}$, corresponding to the respective components of p_i, p_j, p_z, p_l .

Similarly, for any point $p_{any} = [x_{any}, y_{any}, z_{any}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$, its representation in the complex coordinate form on the x - y plane is denoted as $p_{any}^{xy} = x_{any} + y_{any}i \in \mathbb{C}$, and its component along the z -axis is $z_{any} \in \mathbb{R}$, which will not be reiterated in the following discussions.

Given that the relative positions of nodes i, j , and k in the local coordinate frame Σ_l are $p_{li} = [x_{li}, y_{li}, z_{li}]^T$, $p_{lj} = [x_{lj}, y_{lj}, z_{lj}]^T$, and $p_{lk} = [x_{lk}, y_{lk}, z_{lk}]^T$, respectively, and that the rotation matrix aligning the local coordinate frame Σ_l with a new frame Σ_{lz} — in which the z -axis is oriented opposite to the direction of gravity — is denoted

by R_l^{cor} , the relative positions of nodes i, j , and k in the corrected local coordinate frame Σ_{lz} are given by Eqs. (40), (41), and (42), respectively.

$$p_{li}^{cor} = (R_l^{cor})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x_{li} \\ y_{li} \\ z_{li} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{li}^{cor} \\ y_{li}^{cor} \\ z_{li}^{cor} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (40)$$

$$p_{lj}^{cor} = (R_l^{cor})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x_{lj} \\ y_{lj} \\ z_{lj} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{lj}^{cor} \\ y_{lj}^{cor} \\ z_{lj}^{cor} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (41)$$

$$p_{lk}^{cor} = (R_l^{cor})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x_{lk} \\ y_{lk} \\ z_{lk} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{lk}^{cor} \\ y_{lk}^{cor} \\ z_{lk}^{cor} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (42)$$

As shown in Eqs. (43), (44), and (45), the shape constraints of triangle $\triangle ijl$ in the global coordinate system, represented by the coordinates p_i, p_j , and p_l , can be expressed using three linear equations.

$$p_j^{xy} - p_l^{xy} = \omega_{ilj}^{xy} (p_i^{xy} - p_l^{xy}), \quad (43)$$

$$z_l - z_i = z_{il}^{cor}, \quad (44)$$

$$z_l - z_j = z_{jl}^{cor}. \quad (45)$$

Similarly, as indicated in Eqs. (46), (47), and (48), the shape constraints of triangle $\triangle ikl$ in the global coordinate system, defined by the coordinates p_i, p_k , and p_l , can also be formulated using three linear equations.

$$p_k^{xy} - p_l^{xy} = \omega_{ilk}^{xy} (p_i^{xy} - p_l^{xy}), \quad (46)$$

$$z_l - z_i = z_{il}^{cor}, \quad (47)$$

$$z_l - z_k = z_{kl}^{cor}. \quad (48)$$

Furthermore, as presented in Eqs (49), (50), and (51), the shape constraints of triangle $\triangle jkl$, with global coordinates p_j, p_k , and p_l , can likewise be represented by three linear equations.

$$p_k^{xy} - p_l^{xy} = \omega_{jlk}^{xy} (p_j^{xy} - p_l^{xy}), \quad (49)$$

$$z_l - z_j = z_{jl}^{cor}, \quad (50)$$

$$z_l - z_k = z_{kl}^{\text{cor}}. \quad (51)$$

It can be observed that Eq. (44) is identical to Eq. (47), Eq. (45) is identical to Eq. (50), and Eq. (48) is identical to Eq. (51). Therefore, the shape of an arbitrary tetrahedron $ijkl$ can be represented using six linear equations, specifically Eqs. (43), (46), (49), (44), (45), and (47). In fact, as discussed in the previous section, the linear equations of a spatial triangle not only constrain the shape formed by three vertices (denoted as nodes i , j , and k), but also constrain their relative positioning in the vertical direction. Consequently, for a tetrahedron $ijkl$, the shape and vertical configuration in space can be determined using the linear equations corresponding to only two of its triangular facets, such as $\triangle ij l$ and $\triangle ik l$. However, to enhance the robustness of the linear equations against noise from all directions, the linear equations of three triangular facets — namely, $\triangle ij l$, $\triangle ik l$, and $\triangle jk l$ — are still employed to represent the tetrahedron $ijkl$.

For the tetrahedron $ijkl$, the geometric relationship among the four node coordinates $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_k, \mathbf{p}_l$ is represented using the linear equations associated with three of its triangular faces, namely, $\triangle ij l$, $\triangle ik l$, and $\triangle jk l$. The geometric interpretation of these linear equations is provided below. According to the previous section, each spatial triangle, such as $\triangle ij l$, corresponds to three linear equations, which together determine the relative vertical arrangement of nodes i , j , and l , as well as the shape in the x - y plane (i.e., a similar triangle). Accordingly, the tetrahedron $ijkl$ corresponds to six linear equations. These six equations collectively determine the relative vertical positioning of nodes i , j , k , and l , along with the configuration in the x - y plane, preserving the similarity of triangles.

In the tetrahedron $ijkl$ in three-dimensional space, if the coordinates of nodes i , j , and k are known as $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$, the coordinates of node l , denoted by $\mathbf{p}_l \in \mathbb{R}^3$, can be computed using the linear equations of three triangles: $\triangle ij l$, $\triangle ik l$, and $\triangle jk l$. In practice, according to the spatial constraints of a triangle, the coordinates of node l can generally be determined using the linear equation of a single triangle, such as $\triangle ij l$. However, the use of only one triangle, such as $\triangle ij l$, requires that nodes i and j are not coincident and do not lie on a vertical line. To avoid these special cases and to enhance the robustness of the linear system against directional noise, the linear equations corresponding to all three triangles — $\triangle ij l$, $\triangle ik l$, and $\triangle jk l$ — are employed, yielding a total of six linear equations to determine the coordinates of node l .

A specific condition for the localizability problem is presented as follows. In the tetrahedron $ijkl$ embedded in three-dimensional space, the coordinates of nodes i , j , and k are known as $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The coordinate of node l , denoted as $\mathbf{p}_l \in \mathbb{R}^3$, is computed using linear equations derived from the three triangular faces: $\triangle ij l$, $\triangle ik l$, and $\triangle jk l$. If the area of triangle $\triangle ijk$, denoted as S_{ijk} , is non-zero, then node l is localizable. The proof is as follows. Since

Feature point type	Pose estimation algorithm
2D–2D	Epipolar geometry
2D–2D (Planar)	Homography
2D–3D	DLT algorithm, EPnP algorithm
3D–3D	ICP algorithm (Iterative closest point)

Table 2

Pose estimation algorithms corresponding to different types of feature points

$S_{ijk} \neq 0$, nodes i , j , and k are not collinear, and no two of them coincide. Consequently, nodes i , j , and k do not lie on the same vertical line. Therefore, there exist at least two nodes (e.g., nodes i and j) that are neither vertically aligned nor coincident. According to the localization conditions for triangles in three-dimensional space, the coordinate of node k can thus be determined using nodes i and j .

3.3. Representation of pose transformation using linear equations

3.3.1. Construction of linear equations

In SLAM algorithms, various methods can be employed to estimate the pose transformation between two keyframes in three-dimensional space, represented by the rotation-translation matrix $\mathbf{T} \in \text{SE}(3)$. Table 2 presents different types of feature points obtained using a camera sensor, along with the corresponding algorithms that can be applied to compute the pose transformation.

Similarly, when point clouds from two frames are obtained using a LiDAR sensor, a variety of point cloud registration algorithms can be utilized to estimate the pose transformation. In addition, pose transformations between two frames can also be derived using other sources such as IMU sensors, GPS sensors, wheel odometry, and loop closure detection.

Regardless of the type of sensor utilized, the initial information obtained invariably consists of the relative pose transformation between two keyframes (nodes). The objective of back-end optimization is to estimate an accurate global map using these relative pose transformations.

The relative pose transformation between any two nodes (node i and node j), denoted as $\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \text{SE}(3)$, is converted into a set of linear equation constraints. As illustrated in Fig. 5, given the global position of node i as $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$, a virtual node i_x is introduced along the x -axis of the local coordinate frame Σ_i , with global position $\mathbf{p}_{i_x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, satisfying the condition $\|\mathbf{p}_{i_x} - \mathbf{p}_i\| = 1$. Similarly, a virtual node i_y is placed along the y -axis of Σ_i , with global position $\mathbf{p}_{i_y} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, such that $\|\mathbf{p}_{i_y} - \mathbf{p}_i\| = 1$; and a virtual node i_z is defined along the z -axis of Σ_i , with global position $\mathbf{p}_{i_z} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, satisfying $\|\mathbf{p}_{i_z} - \mathbf{p}_i\| = 1$. In the local coordinate frame Σ_i , node i is located at the origin, while nodes i_x , i_y , and i_z represent unit vectors along the x , y , and z axes, respectively.

The global coordinate of node j is denoted as $\mathbf{p}_j \in \mathbb{R}^3$. A virtual node j_x is assumed to lie along the x -axis of the local coordinate system Σ_j , with a global position given

by $\mathbf{p}_{j_x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, satisfying the condition $\|\mathbf{p}_{j_x} - \mathbf{p}_j\| = 1$. Similarly, a virtual node j_y is defined along the y -axis of Σ_j , with global coordinates $\mathbf{p}_{j_y} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\|\mathbf{p}_{j_y} - \mathbf{p}_j\| = 1$. In the same manner, a virtual node j_z is positioned along the z -axis of Σ_j , with global coordinates $\mathbf{p}_{j_z} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and satisfying $\|\mathbf{p}_{j_z} - \mathbf{p}_j\| = 1$. Accordingly, in the local coordinate system Σ_j , node j serves as the origin, while j_x , j_y , and j_z represent the unit vectors along the x -, y -, and z -axes, respectively.

Given the global coordinates of all points in the local coordinate system Σ_i (i.e., $\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}$), a set of linear equations needs to be formulated to represent the global coordinates of all points in the local coordinate system Σ_j (i.e., $\mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_{j_x}, \mathbf{p}_{j_y}, \mathbf{p}_{j_z}$). In this manner, the global coordinates of all nodes can be recursively determined, starting from the first node.

Given the global coordinates of three nodes $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}$ in the local coordinate system Σ_i , the global coordinate of the virtual node j_x in the local coordinate system Σ_j , denoted as \mathbf{p}_{j_x} , is constructed using a system of linear equations. As shown in Eqs. (52) and (53), the linear formulation of a tetrahedron is adopted to derive the equations corresponding to three triangles: $\triangle j_x - i_x - i_y$, $\triangle j_x - i_x - i_z$, and $\triangle j_x - i_y - i_z$.

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_x i_y} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_x i_z} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy} = \omega_{i_y j_x i_z} (p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy}) \end{cases} \quad (52)$$

$$\begin{cases} z_{j_x} - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x j_x}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_x} - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y j_x}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_x} - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z j_x}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

The variables $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}, p_{j_x}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ represent the complex coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_x , respectively, projected onto the horizontal plane. The variables $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_{j_x} \in \mathbb{R}$ denote the vertical coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_x , respectively. The complex coordinate $p_{j_x}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ and the vertical coordinate $z_{j_x} \in \mathbb{R}$ together define the global coordinate $\mathbf{p}_{j_x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ of node j_x . The parameters $\omega_{i_x j_x i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_x i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_x i_z} \in \mathbb{C}$ and $z_{i_x j_x}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_x}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_x}^{\text{cor}} \in \mathbb{R}$ will be specified in detail in subsequent sections.

Subsequently, the virtual node coordinate \mathbf{p}_{j_y} from Σ_j and the three points $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}$ from Σ_i are utilized to construct a system of linear equations. As shown in Eqs. (54) and (55), the formulation is based on the representation of a tetrahedral equation. Specifically, linear equations are constructed for the three triangles: $\triangle j_y - i_x - i_y$, $\triangle j_y - i_x - i_z$, and $\triangle j_y - i_y - i_z$.

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_y i_y} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_y i_z} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy} = \omega_{i_y j_y i_z} (p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy}) \end{cases} \quad (54)$$

$$\begin{cases} z_{j_y} - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x j_y}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_y} - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y j_y}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_y} - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z j_y}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases} \quad (55)$$

Here, $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}, p_{j_y}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ denote the complex coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_y projected onto the ground plane, respectively; $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_{j_y} \in \mathbb{R}$ represent the vertical coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_y , respectively. The complex coordinate $p_{j_y}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ corresponds to the projection of the node j_y onto the ground plane to be determined, and $z_{j_y} \in \mathbb{R}$ is its vertical coordinate. Together, they define the global coordinate of node j_y , denoted as $\mathbf{p}_{j_y} \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The parameters $\omega_{i_x j_y i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_y i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_y i_z} \in \mathbb{C}$ and $z_{i_x j_y}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_y}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_y}^{\text{cor}} \in \mathbb{R}$ will be specified in detail in subsequent sections.

Subsequently, a set of linear equations is constructed using the virtual node coordinate \mathbf{p}_{j_z} from Σ_j and the three points $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}$ from Σ_i . As shown in Eqs. (56) and (57), the tetrahedral formulation is employed to derive the linear equations corresponding to three triangles: $\triangle j_z - i_x - i_y$, $\triangle j_z - i_x - i_z$, and $\triangle j_z - i_y - i_z$.

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_z i_y} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_z i_z} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy} = \omega_{i_y j_z i_z} (p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy}) \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

$$\begin{cases} z_{j_z} - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x j_z}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_z} - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y j_z}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_z} - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z j_z}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases} \quad (57)$$

The variables $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}, p_{j_z}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ represent the complex coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z , and j_z , respectively, projected onto the horizontal plane. The variables $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_{j_z} \in \mathbb{R}$ denote the vertical coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z , and j_z , respectively. The complex coordinate $p_{j_z}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ and the vertical coordinate $z_{j_z} \in \mathbb{R}$ together determine the global coordinate of node j_z , denoted as $\mathbf{p}_{j_z} \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The parameters $\omega_{i_x j_z i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_z i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_z i_z} \in \mathbb{C}$ and $z_{i_x j_z}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_z}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_z}^{\text{cor}} \in \mathbb{R}$ will be specified in detail in subsequent sections.

Subsequently, the nodal coordinate \mathbf{p}_i from Σ_i and the three points $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}$ are employed to construct linear

equations. As shown in Eqs. (58) and (59), the formulation of the tetrahedral equation is utilized to derive the linear equations corresponding to three triangles: $\triangle i - i_x - i_y$, $\triangle i - i_x - i_z$, and $\triangle i - i_y - i_z$.

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{\text{xy}} - p_i^{\text{xy}} = \omega_{i_x, i_y} (p_{i_x}^{\text{xy}} - p_i^{\text{xy}}) \\ p_{i_z}^{\text{xy}} - p_i^{\text{xy}} = \omega_{i_x, i_z} (p_{i_x}^{\text{xy}} - p_i^{\text{xy}}) \\ p_{i_z}^{\text{xy}} - p_i^{\text{xy}} = \omega_{i_y, i_z} (p_{i_y}^{\text{xy}} - p_i^{\text{xy}}) \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

$$\begin{cases} z_i - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x, i}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_i - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y, i}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_i - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z, i}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases} \quad (59)$$

The variables $p_{i_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{i_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{i_z}^{\text{xy}}, p_i^{\text{xy}} \in \mathbb{C}$ denote the complex coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z , and i , respectively, projected onto the horizontal plane. The corresponding vertical coordinates of these nodes, $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_i \in \mathbb{R}$, represent their positions along the vertical axis. The variable $p_i^{\text{xy}} \in \mathbb{C}$ denotes the complex coordinate of the target node i projected onto the horizontal plane, while $z_i \in \mathbb{R}$ represents its vertical coordinate; together, they define the global coordinate of node i as $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The parameters $\omega_{i_x, i_y}, \omega_{i_x, i_z}, \omega_{i_y, i_z} \in \mathbb{C}$ and $z_{i_x, i}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y, i}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z, i}^{\text{cor}} \in \mathbb{R}$ will be specified in detail in subsequent sections.

The node i in the local coordinate system Σ_i , along with three virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z in Σ_j , has been represented using the three virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in the local coordinate system Σ_i . Since the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z correspond to unit vectors along the three axes of Σ_i , the area of the triangle $\triangle i_x - i_y - i_z$, denoted as S_{i_x, i_y, i_z} , is non-zero, which satisfies the localizability condition of a tetrahedron. Given the global coordinates of the three virtual nodes in Σ_i , namely $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}$, it is possible to compute the global coordinates of node j in Σ_j , as well as those of its three virtual nodes $\mathbf{p}_{j_x}, \mathbf{p}_{j_y}, \mathbf{p}_{j_z}$. By iterating this process sequentially, all nodes (keyframes) in the SLAM problem can be connected in a chain. If the pose of the first node is known — i.e., the global coordinates of node 1, \mathbf{p}_1 , and those of its three virtual nodes, $\mathbf{p}_{1_x}, \mathbf{p}_{1_y}, \mathbf{p}_{1_z}$ — then the pose of any node i can be computed, including the global coordinates of node i , \mathbf{p}_i , and its three virtual nodes, $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}$.

Given the global coordinates of the three virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in the local coordinate system Σ_i , the global coordinates of the three virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z in the local coordinate system Σ_j can be computed using a set of linear equations. In the following, the inverse representation problem is considered: assuming the global coordinates of the virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z in Σ_j are known, it is examined whether the global coordinates of the nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in Σ_i can be similarly computed using the aforementioned linear equations.

The geometric interpretation of these linear equations can be analyzed. Specifically, the six linear equations corresponding to the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$ impose constraints on the relative distances of the nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_x along the vertical direction, as well as the shape of their projection onto the x - y plane, which are determined by similarity of triangles. If these geometric constraints are relaxed such that the relative distances along the vertical direction are replaced by proportional relationships, then the linear equations constrain the shape of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$, while allowing its overall scale to vary.

Similarly, the other sets of linear equations constrain the shapes (but not the scales) of the tetrahedra $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_y$ and $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_z$. Consequently, the geometric configuration formed by the six nodes $i_x, i_y, i_z, j_x, j_y, j_z$ is uniquely determined in terms of shape, although its scale remains unspecified. Therefore, given the global coordinates of the virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z , the global coordinates of the nodes i_x, i_y, i_z can also be computed using the same system of linear equations.

In conclusion, the 18 linear equations corresponding to the three tetrahedra — namely, $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$, $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_y$, and $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_z$ — can be equivalently used to represent the pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} , with the scale on the x - y plane to be computed subsequently.

In the aforementioned system of linear equations, the three virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in the local coordinate frame Σ_i are employed to represent the three virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z in the local coordinate frame Σ_j . To ensure symmetry, it is also possible to represent the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in Σ_i using the virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z in Σ_j , and to formulate the corresponding set of 18 linear equations. However, as previously demonstrated, the 18 linear equations that express the nodes j_x, j_y, j_z in terms of i_x, i_y, i_z are already sufficient to equivalently represent the pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} . Therefore, the additional representation of i_x, i_y, i_z using j_x, j_y, j_z is redundant.

In the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, the set \mathcal{V} represents all nodes (keyframes). Let there be n nodes in \mathcal{V} . Since three virtual nodes i_x, i_y , and i_z are defined in the local coordinate system Σ_i of each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$, the set of virtual nodes is defined as $\mathcal{V}_v = \{i_x, i_y, i_z \mid i \in \mathcal{V}\}$. The 3D coordinates of these virtual nodes are given by $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v$. The planar coordinates of the virtual nodes are denoted as $p_{i_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{i_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{i_z}^{\text{xy}} \in \mathbb{C} \mid i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v$, and their vertical coordinates are represented by $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}$ for $i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v$. The coordinate vector of all virtual nodes is defined as $\mathbf{p}_v = [p_{1_x}^T, p_{1_y}^T, p_{1_z}^T, \dots, p_{n_x}^T, p_{n_y}^T, p_{n_z}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times n}$. The planar coordinate vector of the virtual nodes is given by $\mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = [p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}}, \dots, p_{n_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{n_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{n_z}^{\text{xy}}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^n$, and the vertical coordinate vector is defined as $\mathbf{p}_v^z = [z_{1_x}, z_{1_y}, z_{1_z}, \dots, z_{n_x}, z_{n_y}, z_{n_z}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Let the set of all pose transformations $\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \text{SE}(3)$ be denoted as $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \text{SE}(3) \mid i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$. Each pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} between any two nodes (node i and node j) can be

reformulated into 18 linear equations, consisting of 9 planar coordinate equations and 9 vertical coordinate equations. Accordingly, the system of linear equations corresponding to all pose transformations $T_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}$ is represented by Eqs. (60) and (61).

$$\mathbf{A}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}^{\text{xy}}, \quad (60)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z = \mathbf{b}^z. \quad (61)$$

In addition, the coordinates of node i are represented using the coordinates of three virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z defined in the local coordinate system Σ_i . Once the coordinates of all virtual nodes, denoted as \mathbf{p}_v , have been determined, the coordinates of each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ can subsequently be computed from \mathbf{p}_v . Let the coordinate vector of all nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$ be defined as $\mathbf{p} = [\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_n] \in \mathbf{R}^{3 \times n}$. The planar coordinate vector of all nodes is defined as $\mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = [p_1^{\text{xy}}, p_2^{\text{xy}}, \dots, p_n^{\text{xy}}]^T \in \mathbf{C}^n$, and the vertical coordinate vector is defined as $\mathbf{p}^z = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n]^T \in \mathbf{R}^n$. Accordingly, the equations for computing the node coordinates \mathbf{p}^{xy} and \mathbf{p}^z from the virtual node coordinates \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} and \mathbf{p}_v^z are given as Eqs. (62) and (63).

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{D}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}}, \quad (62)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^z \mathbf{p}^z = \mathbf{D}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z. \quad (63)$$

The pseudocode of the proposed algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1 in Supplementary Material S1.

3.3.2. Computation of paramters

In the previous section, the pose transformation T_{ij} was represented by linear equations constructed from four tetrahedra (tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$, tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_y$, tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_z$, and tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - i$). Each tetrahedron was used to formulate the linear equations following the method described in Sec. 3.2.3, and the specific computational steps for the parameters of these equations are provided in the Sec. A in Appendix.

3.4. Pose transformation across different sensors

3.4.1. GPS sensors

The proposed algorithm converts input data from various heterogeneous sensors into a unified set of linear equation constraints, followed by back-end optimization in SLAM. The non-GPS sensors include cameras, LiDAR, IMU sensors, wheel encoders, and loop closure detections. The input data from these sensors are processed by the SLAM front-end module to obtain the pose transformations T_{ij} . The procedure for converting the pose transformations T_{ij} into linear equations has been discussed in previous sections.

The case of the GPS sensor is relatively special. First, the data obtained from the GPS sensor consist of longitude

and latitude values, which define a fixed coordinate system (the geographic coordinate system). Second, the longitude and latitude information acquired by the GPS sensor contains only translational information and lacks rotational information, making it impossible to convert it into a pose transformation T_{ij} . To address this issue, three GPS data points are selected to form a planar or spatial triangle, and linear equations are then constructed following the method described in Sec. 3.2.1. Through this approach, the GPS data can be converted into the linear equations expressed in Eq. (64).

$$\mathbf{E}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = 0, \quad (64)$$

where $\mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} \in \mathbf{C}^n$ denotes the planar coordinate vector of all nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$. Two types of linear equations are constructed, namely the linear equations derived from adjacent GPS data and those derived from cross-node GPS data. Further details are provided in the Sec. B in Appendix.

3.4.2. Variance of pose transformation

The pose transformation between two frames can be obtained through various sensors, including cameras, LiDAR, IMU, GPS, wheel encoders, and loop closure detection. Typically, the pose transformations derived from different sensors are associated with different levels of uncertainty; thus, the variance for each sensor can be predefined based on its intrinsic characteristics. Alternatively, the variance of the pose transformation T_{ij} can be computed during the estimation process within the front-end module of the SLAM algorithm. The pose transformation matrix T_{ij} is a 4×4 matrix. For the sake of simplicity, a single variance value σ_{ij}^2 is employed to represent the uncertainty of the entire pose transformation matrix.

The linear equations between each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ and the virtual nodes $i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v$ are given by Eqs. (65), (66), (67), (68), and (69).

$$\mathbf{A}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_1, \quad (65)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z = \mathbf{b}^z + \mathbf{v}_2, \quad (66)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{D}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_3, \quad (67)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^z \mathbf{p}^z = \mathbf{D}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z + \mathbf{v}_4, \quad (68)$$

$$\mathbf{E}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{v}_5. \quad (69)$$

The error vectors are distributed as $\mathbf{v}_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_i), i \in [1, 5]$. For the covariance matrices Σ_1 and Σ_2 corresponding

to the error vectors \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 , the variance σ_{ij}^2 of the associated pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} is adopted as the variance of the respective linear equations. In contrast, the covariance matrices Σ_3 and Σ_4 for the error vectors \mathbf{v}_3 and \mathbf{v}_4 are set to zero, as these two systems of linear equations represent the expression of node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ in terms of its virtual coordinates i_x, i_y, i_z , without incorporating any observational data. For the error vector \mathbf{v}_5 , each linear equation is constructed using two pose transformations (e.g., \mathbf{T}_{ij} and \mathbf{T}_{ik}). For simplicity, the variance of the corresponding linear equation is defined as $\sigma^2 = \sigma_{ij}^2 + \sigma_{ik}^2$.

3.5. Map Scale Estimation

3.5.1. In the absence of GPS sensors

The pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} is converted into a set of linear equations (65), (66), (67), (68). However, the geometric structure formed by the nodes constrained by these equations does not restrict the overall scale of the map. Consequently, a uniform scaling of all nodes in the map does not violate these linear equations. To compute the global coordinates of all nodes, the coordinates of all points in the reference frame Σ_1 (i.e., nodes 1, $1_x, 1_y, 1_z$) are substituted as constants into the linear equations (65), (66), (67), (68). Nevertheless, in order to optimize the scale of the entire map, the coordinates of all points in the reference frame Σ_1 are treated as variables parameterized by the scale factor ρ and then substituted into the equations. An error function is subsequently constructed to optimize the map scale ρ .

Once the optimal scale factor ρ is obtained, the coordinates of all nodes in the reference frame Σ_1 ($\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_{1_x}, \mathbf{p}_{1_y}, \mathbf{p}_{1_z}$) can be determined. Let the planar coordinate vector of the virtual nodes $i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{1_x, 1_y, 1_z\}$ be denoted as $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} = [p_{2_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{2_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{2_z}^{\text{xy}}, \dots, p_{n_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{n_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{n_z}^{\text{xy}}] \in \mathbb{C}^{3n-3}$. By substituting the planar coordinates $p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}}$ into the system, the linear equation $\mathbf{A}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_1$ is transformed into the form shown in Eq. (70).

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}1}, \quad (70)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}1} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_{\text{sub}1})$ denotes the noise associated with each linear equation. The variance of each equation is represented by the variance σ_{ij}^2 of the corresponding pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} . The number of linear equations in the system remains unchanged, and the variance associated with each equation is not modified. Therefore, the error vector satisfies $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}1} = \mathbf{v}_1$, and the covariance matrix is given by $\Sigma_{\text{sub}1} = \Sigma_1$. The least-squares solution of the linear system is expressed as Eq. (71).

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} = ((\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^T (\Sigma_1)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^{-1} (\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^T (\Sigma_1)^{-1} \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}. \quad (71)$$

Given that the vertical coordinates of node 1, node 1_x , node 1_y , and node 1_z are $z_1 = 0, z_{1_x} = 0, z_{1_y} = 0$, and $z_{1_z} = 1$, respectively, the planar coordinates of z_{1_x}, z_{1_y} , and z_{1_z} are substituted into the equation. As a result, the linear system $\mathbf{A}^z \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = \mathbf{b}^z + \mathbf{v}_2$ is transformed into Eq. (??).

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^z + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2}, \quad (72)$$

where the coordinate vector is given by $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = [z_{2_x}, z_{2_y}, z_{2_z}, \dots, z_{n_x}, z_{n_y}, z_{n_z}] \in \mathbb{R}^{3n-3}$; $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_{\text{sub}2})$ denotes the noise associated with each linear equation. The number of linear equations in the system remains unchanged, and the variance corresponding to each equation is also preserved. Therefore, the error vector satisfies $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2} = \mathbf{v}_2$, and the covariance matrix satisfies $\Sigma_{\text{sub}2} = \Sigma_2$. The least squares solution of the linear system is given by Eq. (115).

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = ((\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z)^T (\Sigma_2)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z)^{-1} (\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z)^T (\Sigma_2)^{-1} \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^z. \quad (73)$$

More detailed information is provided in the Sec. C in the Appendix.

3.5.2. In the Presence of GPS sensors

In the case where GPS sensors are employed, the linear equations between each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ and its corresponding virtual nodes $i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v$ must be further augmented by the following expression, as defined in Eq. (69).

Originally, Eq. (70) allows for the independent computation of the coordinate vector \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} . Subsequently, by substituting the computed \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} into Eq. (67), the coordinate vector \mathbf{p}^{xy} can be obtained. However, Eq. (69) imposes an additional constraint on \mathbf{p}^{xy} . Therefore, it is necessary to solve Eqs. (70), (67), and (69) simultaneously to determine the node vectors \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} and \mathbf{p}^{xy} .

In contrast, the computation procedure for the vertical coordinate vectors \mathbf{p}_v^z and \mathbf{p}^z remains unchanged. Specifically, \mathbf{p}_v^z can be independently computed using Eq. (72), and the resulting \mathbf{p}_v^z can then be substituted into Eq. (68) to obtain the coordinate vector \mathbf{p}^z .

Let the coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}_{\text{acc}}^{\text{xy}} = [(\mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}})^T, (\mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}})^T]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{4n}$ be defined as the concatenated vector of \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} and \mathbf{p}^{xy} . Accordingly, Eqs. (70), (67), and (69) are combined into Eq. (74).

$$\mathbf{F}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_{\text{acc}}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{G}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_6, \quad (74)$$

where the error vector is defined as $\mathbf{v}_6 = [\mathbf{v}_1^T, \mathbf{v}_3^T, \mathbf{v}_5^T]^T$, and it follows a normal distribution, i.e., $\mathbf{v}_6 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_6)$. Under the assumption that the individual linear equations are independent, the covariance matrix Σ_6 is a diagonal matrix, given by $\Sigma_6 = \text{diag}\{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_3, \Sigma_5\}$.

By substituting the planar coordinates $p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}}$ into Eq. (74), the equation is transformed into Eq. (75).

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub,acc}}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{G}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}6}. \quad (75)$$

The coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub,acc}}^{\text{xy}} \in \mathbb{C}^{4n-4}$ is obtained by removing the elements $p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}}$ from the coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}_{\text{acc}}^{\text{xy}}$. The error vector $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}6} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_{\text{sub}6})$ represents

the noise associated with each linear equation. The number of linear equations in the system remains unchanged, and the variance corresponding to each equation is also preserved. Therefore, the error vector satisfies $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}6} = \mathbf{v}_6$, and the covariance matrix satisfies $\Sigma_{\text{sub}6} = \Sigma_6$. The least squares solution of the linear system is given by Eq. (76).

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub,acc}}^{\text{xy}} = ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^T (\Sigma_6)^{-1} \mathbf{F}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^{-1} (\mathbf{F}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^T (\Sigma_6)^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}. \quad (76)$$

The pseudocode for computing the map scale and node coordinates is presented in Algorithm 6 in Supplementary Material S1.

3.6. Outlier removal

In this study, the linear equations are constructed based on the pose transformations \mathbf{T}_{ij} between nodes. If outliers exist in the set of pose transformations $\mathcal{E} = \mathbf{T}_{ij}, i, j \in \mathcal{V}$ within the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, the corresponding coefficients in the linear equations will also contain outliers. To address this issue, the method proposed in Wu (2025) is employed to remove the outliers, with further details provided in the Sec. refsec:sec10 in the Appendix.

3.7. Estimation of local coordinate systems

The coordinates of each node in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ within the global coordinate system Σ_g have been computed as $\mathbf{p} = [\mathbf{p}_1^T, \mathbf{p}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{p}_n^T] \in \mathbb{R}^{3n}$. In addition, it is necessary to estimate the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i of the local coordinate system Σ_i , represented by node i , with respect to the global coordinate system Σ_g . To achieve this, the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm for point set registration is employed, and the detailed procedure is provided in the Sec. E in Appendix.

4. Theoretical analysis of computational complexity

Several methods were explored for solving the system of linear equations. The sparse Cholesky decomposition demonstrated faster computation when the matrix dimension was relatively low, whereas the conjugate gradient method exhibited superior performance for higher-dimensional matrices, as detailed in in Sec. F in Appendix. In addition, the proposed algorithm can be extended to both global and local optimization schemes, with a brief discussion provided in Sec. G in Appendix.

In the factor graph optimization method, let the number of nodes be denoted as n , with each node corresponding to a Lie algebra vector of six dimensions. Therefore, the total number of unknown variables is $6n$. Let the number of pose constraints be m , implying that the number of error terms is also m . The objective error function to be minimized is defined as in Eq. (77).

$$J_g(\mathbf{x}_g) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} e_i(\mathbf{x}_g)^T \Sigma_g e_i(\mathbf{x}_g), \quad (77)$$

where \mathbf{x}_g represents a vector of dimension $6n$. A first-order Taylor expansion is then applied to the error term $e_i(\mathbf{x}_g)$, yielding the approximated error term as shown in Eq. (78).

$$e_i(\mathbf{x}_g + \Delta_x) \approx e_i(\mathbf{x}_g) + \mathbf{J}_i \Delta_x. \quad (78)$$

Consequently, the entire error function can be approximated as given in Eq. (79).

$$J_g(\mathbf{x}_g + \Delta_x) \approx \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} (e_i(\mathbf{x}_g) + \mathbf{J}_i \Delta_x)^T \Sigma_g (e_i(\mathbf{x}_g) + \mathbf{J}_i \Delta_x). \quad (79)$$

To minimize the error function J_g , the linear system that must be solved at each iteration is given by Eqs. (80) and (81).

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{H}_g = \mathbf{J}_i^T \Sigma_g^{-1} \mathbf{J}_i \\ \mathbf{b}_g = \mathbf{J}_i^T \Sigma_g^{-1} (-e_i(\mathbf{x}_g)) \end{cases}, \quad (80)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_g \Delta_x = \mathbf{b}_g. \quad (81)$$

In the proposed algorithm (in the absence of GPS sensors), the real-valued matrix $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ has dimensions of $18m \times 6(n-1)$, while the real-valued matrix $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z$ has dimensions of $9m \times 3(n-1)$. The matrix \mathbf{H}_1 is of size $6(n-1) \times 6(n-1)$, and the matrix \mathbf{H}_2 is of size $3(n-1) \times 3(n-1)$. In the Hessian matrix computation stage, the proposed method requires the multiplication of a $6(n-1) \times 18m$ matrix with a $18m \times 6(n-1)$ matrix, as well as the multiplication of a $3(n-1) \times 9m$ matrix with a $9m \times 3(n-1)$ matrix. In contrast, the graph optimization algorithm involves the multiplication of a $6n \times m$ matrix with an $m \times 6n$ matrix. Since the number of poses m is generally much greater than the number of nodes n , the computational complexity is primarily determined by m . As a result, the computational cost of the proposed algorithm is higher than that of the graph optimization algorithm.

In the linear equation computation stage, the proposed algorithm requires solving a linear system with a coefficient matrix \mathbf{H}_1 of dimension $6(n-1) \times 6(n-1)$ and a matrix \mathbf{H}_2 of dimension $3(n-1) \times 3(n-1)$. In contrast, the graph optimization algorithm involves solving a linear system with a coefficient matrix \mathbf{H}_g of dimension $6n \times 6n$. Moreover, the proposed algorithm is non-iterative, whereas the graph optimization algorithm typically requires approximately 10 to 15 iterations to converge.

Based on the above analysis, it can be estimated that the computational cost of the proposed linear equation algorithm is roughly equivalent to that of 2 to 3 iterations of the graph optimization algorithm, while the latter generally requires 10 to 15 iterations.

5. Experimental results and analysis

5.1. Experimental design

The objective of this study is to evaluate the accuracy and computational efficiency of the proposed back-end optimization algorithm. Therefore, a complete SLAM system was not

implemented. Instead, randomly generated trajectories were utilized to validate the back-end optimization algorithm. In the experiments, the input data consist of randomly generated trajectories (used as groundtruth) and the corresponding pose constraints. The estimated trajectories were then computed using both the proposed algorithm and the graph optimization library GTSAM. Fig. 6 presents an example in which the accurately estimated trajectory nearly overlaps with the groundtruth trajectory. In contrast, Fig. 7 shows an example of a coarsely estimated trajectory that does not fully align with the groundtruth.

The randomly generated trajectories are described as follows. The function `erdos_renyi_graph(num_nodes, edge_density, directed=False)` from the NetworkX library is employed to generate the random trajectories. Here, `num_nodes` denotes the number of nodes, and `edge_density` represents the probability that an edge exists between any pair of nodes. For instance, setting `edge_density=0.1` indicates that there is a 10% probability of an edge (representing a pose constraint) existing between any two nodes. The parameter `directed=False` specifies that the generated graph is undirected.

To better approximate the characteristics of graphs encountered in SLAM problems, the randomly generated graphs described above were modified as follows. First, in SLAM scenarios, there is often more than one edge (i.e., pose constraint) between two nodes. For example, multiple pose transformations may be obtained between two adjacent nodes through feature point matching, IMU sensors, and GPS data. Therefore, each edge generated by the NetworkX library was expanded into three edges, with each edge representing a distinct pose transformation. Furthermore, to ensure that the generated graph is connected, it was verified whether an edge exists between any two consecutively indexed nodes (e.g., node i and node $i + 1$). If no such edge was found, one was added. This modification reflects the fact that in SLAM problems, there must be a pose constraint between any two consecutively indexed nodes; otherwise, the resulting graph may be non-computable.

The pose of each node in its local coordinate system is randomly generated. The rotation matrix of the pose is a random rotation matrix, while each component of the translation vector follows a uniform distribution $U(-5, 5)$, where the unit can be considered as meters.

The edge (pose transformation) between any two nodes is computed based on their respective poses. Let the pose of node i be denoted as T_i and that of node j as T_j . The relative pose from node i to node j is expressed as $T_{ij} = (T_i)^{-1}T_j$, while the relative pose from node j to node i is given by $T_{ji} = (T_j)^{-1}T_i$. Random perturbation noise is introduced for each edge, and the rotational component of the perturbation matrix T_{noise} is generated through the following procedure. A rotation vector representation is adopted, where the rotation axis $axis \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is randomly sampled from the unit sphere. The rotation angle θ follows a uniform distribution $U(-\pi/360, \pi/360)$. The rotation vector is then obtained as $v = \theta * axis$. This rotation vector characterizes a

random rotational perturbation with a magnitude within $[-\pi/360, \pi/360]$. Each component of the translation vector in T_{noise} follows a uniform distribution $U(-0.01, 0.01)$, where the unit can be considered meters. Following the same procedure, a subset of randomly selected edges is further perturbed to create outliers (T_{outlier}), in which the rotation angle follows $U(-\pi/4, \pi/4)$ and each component of the translation vector follows $U(-10, 10)$. The number of outliers can be specified and serves as a configurable parameter in the experiments.

The implementation of the proposed algorithm is outlined as follows. The code is written in Python. The representation of graphs and the Dijkstra algorithm used in the outlier removal procedure are implemented using the NetworkX library. The weighted IQR algorithm employed in the outlier removal process is implemented in Python. Since the global optimization component of the outlier removal algorithm can reuse results from the local optimization, and optimizing this component in C++ would require considerable engineering effort, the outlier removal module is excluded from the subsequent computational time comparison.

The pose transformation in the algorithm is converted into linear equation matrices $A_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ and A_{sub}^z , with partial implementation utilizing custom-defined classes. The computation of the linear equations is carried out using the `cholesky` function from the `pyamg` library and the `cg` function from the `scipy.sparse` library, which implement sparse Cholesky decomposition methods. Both libraries are based on and optimized with C++ backends; therefore, the linear equation computation component can be employed for performance comparison with the GTSAM library.

The graph optimization component was implemented using the Python version of the GTSAM library, which is internally developed in C++ and exposes its functionality to Python via Pybind. The experiments were conducted on a host machine equipped with an Intel Core i5 dual-core processor and 16 GB of RAM. Ubuntu 20.04 was run within a VMware virtual machine, with allocated resources of a 2-core CPU and 4 GB of memory. All algorithms were executed within this virtualized environment to ensure the fairness of comparisons.

5.2. Experimental results

5.2.1. Results of trajectory accuracy

The trajectory estimation accuracy of the proposed algorithm is compared with that of the graph optimization algorithm provided by the GTSAM library. Graphs are randomly generated using the aforementioned method, with the number of nodes (`num_nodes`) set to 30 and the edge density (`edge_density`) set to 0.2. If a fully connected graph with 30 nodes is considered, the total number of edges would be $30 \times (30 + 1)/2 = 465$. However, since the graph is not fully connected, the probability of an edge existing between any two nodes is 20%, resulting in an average number of edges equal to $465 \times 0.2 = 93$. Furthermore, as described previously, each edge is expanded into three edges, leading to an actual average edge count of $93 \times 3 = 279$.

In this experiment, the number of outlier edges was used as a variable parameter to evaluate the trajectory accuracy of different algorithms under varying proportions of outlier noise. The proportions of outliers were set to 2%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, corresponding approximately to 6, 14, 28, 42, 56, 70, 84 outlier edges, respectively.

The proposed linear equation algorithm is compared with the graph optimization algorithm provided by the GTSAM library. In the graph optimization framework, various types of robust kernel functions are employed, including the Huber, Tukey, Cauchy, Geman-McClure, Fair, and Welsch kernels. The parameters for these kernel functions are set to their recommended values: for the Huber kernel, $k = 1.345$; for the Tukey kernel, $k = 4.6851$; for the Cauchy kernel, $k = 1.0$; for the Geman-McClure kernel, $k = 1.0$; for the Fair kernel, $k = 1.0$; and for the Welsch kernel, $k = 1.0$.

The results of each optimization algorithm were saved to files and subsequently evaluated using the *evo* tool to compute the RMSE values of the Absolute Pose Error (APE) and Relative Pose Error (RPE) metrics. For each outlier ratio, the experiment was repeated ten times, and the average values of the APE and RPE over the fifty runs were used as the representative results for that outlier ratio. The detailed experimental results are presented in Figs. 8, 9.

5.2.2. Results of computational time

The proposed algorithm is compared with the graph optimization algorithm from the GTSAM library in terms of trajectory estimation computation time. Since the outlier removal component of the proposed method is implemented in Python and has not been optimized for engineering efficiency, and considering that the results from the local optimization stage can typically be reused in the global optimization stage, only the time required for solving the linear equations is included in the computation time of the proposed algorithm. The time for outlier removal and linear equation construction is excluded. Therefore, in this experiment, outlier noise is not added to the pose transformations. The linear equations are solved using both sparse Cholesky decomposition and the conjugate gradient method. For the GTSAM library, only the computation time of the nonlinear optimization is reported (implemented in C++), excluding the time for adding pose constraints (implemented in Python).

Random graphs were generated using the method described above, with the edge density (*edge_density*) set to 0.01, and the number of nodes (*num_nodes*) used as an experimental parameter, taking values of 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000. Fig. 10 and Table 3 present the computation times of the proposed algorithm employing sparse Cholesky decomposition, the conjugate gradient method, and a graph optimization algorithm under varying numbers of nodes.

5.3. Discussion

5.3.1. Discussion of trajectory accuracy

Figs. 8, 9 present the APE and RPE curves for the proposed algorithm (*myalg*) as well as for the Huber and Fair robust kernel functions. Other robust kernel functions

Algorithm/num	200	400	600	800	1000
CG	0.4694	0.5613	0.7741	1.0984	1.4696
Cholesky	0.0262	0.2353	1.2997	4.4045	10.8058
GTSAM	0.0532	0.2965	1.1099	3.2119	7.6762

Note: time unit is second.

Table 3

Computation time for different algorithms

exhibit high sensitivity to parameter settings and yield poor accuracy when default parameters are used; therefore, their results are not included in this section. These robust kernels require data-driven parameter selection based on the actual error distribution. When the proportion of outliers is below 15%, the accuracy of the proposed algorithm is comparable to that of algorithms using the Huber and Fair robust kernels. In this case, the primary sources of error are general noise and the inherent limitations of the linear equation solver. However, when the proportion of outliers exceeds 15%, the error associated with the proposed algorithm increases more significantly compared to the Huber and Fair robust kernel-based methods. This increase is mainly attributed to the outlier removal component within the proposed algorithm. Specifically, when the proportion of outliers surpasses 15%, the recall rate of the outlier removal algorithm can no longer be maintained near 100%, resulting in some outliers being misclassified as inliers and subsequently used in trajectory computation.

5.3.2. Discussion of computational time

Fig. 10 and Table 3 present the computation times of the proposed algorithm employing sparse Cholesky decomposition, the conjugate gradient method, and a graph optimization algorithm under varying numbers of nodes. The results demonstrate that the linear system solution using sparse Cholesky decomposition achieves significantly lower computation time compared to both the graph optimization algorithm and the conjugate gradient method. As the number of nodes increases, the computation time of the sparse Cholesky decomposition method gradually approaches that of the conjugate gradient method, yet remains lower than that of the graph optimization algorithm.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented a novel linear back-end optimization algorithm for three-dimensional SLAM, which reformulates the entire problem into a unified system of linear equations. By introducing virtual coordinate systems to describe spatial relationships through geometric similarity, the method eliminates the need for traditional nonlinear iterative solvers, resulting in improved computational efficiency and stability. Furthermore, by leveraging IMU-derived gravity information, the framework achieves a gravity-aligned linear formulation and seamlessly integrates heterogeneous sensor data — including LiDAR, camera, IMU, GPS, and wheel odometry — within the same linear system for unified multi-sensor fusion.

Extensive experiments demonstrated that the proposed method achieves localization accuracy comparable to state-of-the-art nonlinear graph optimization techniques while requiring only a fraction of the computational cost. In future work, we plan to extend the linear framework to real-world and online SLAM systems, incorporating dynamic scene modeling, GPS-based adaptive scale estimation, and GPU-accelerated implementations. The results suggest that the proposed linear SLAM formulation offers a promising direction for efficient, robust, and scalable back-end optimization in autonomous mapping and navigation.

A. Computation of paramters

A.1. Computation of paramters for the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$

In the preceding section, the linear equations constructed from the three triangular faces of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$ — namely, triangles $\triangle j_x - i_x - i_y$, $\triangle j_x - i_x - i_z$, and $\triangle j_x - i_y - i_z$ — were formulated as shown in Eqs. (52) and (53).

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_x i_y} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_x i_z} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy}), \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy} = \omega_{i_y j_x i_z} (p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_x}^{xy}) \end{cases}, \quad (\text{same as (52)})$$

$$\begin{cases} z_{j_x} - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x j_x}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_x} - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y j_x}^{\text{cor}}, \\ z_{j_x} - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z j_x}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases}, \quad (\text{same as (53)})$$

where $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}, p_{j_x}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ denote the projections of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_x onto the ground plane, respectively. Similarly, let $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_{j_x} \in \mathbb{R}$ represent the vertical coordinates of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_x , respectively. The complex coordinate $p_{j_x}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ corresponds to the projection of the unknown node j_x onto the ground plane, and $z_{j_x} \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes its vertical coordinate. Together, these define the global 3D coordinate $\mathbf{p}_{j_x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ of node j_x . The parameters $\omega_{i_x j_x i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_x i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_x i_z}$ and $z_{i_x j_x}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_x}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_x}^{\text{cor}}$ were not explicitly defined in the preceding sections. In the following, the computation methods for these parameters are provided.

The local coordinate system Σ_i is corrected to a new coordinate system Σ_i^{cor} , in which the z -axis is aligned opposite to the gravity direction measured by the IMU in node i , using a rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$. Let the gravity direction measured by the IMU in node i be denoted as $\mathbf{g}_{\text{ori}}^i = [x_g^i, y_g^i, z_g^i]^T$, and its inverse direction as $\mathbf{g}_{\text{inv}}^i = -\mathbf{g}_{\text{ori}}^i = [-x_g^i, -y_g^i, -z_g^i]^T$. It is assumed that the z -axis of the relative position sensor in node i is aligned with the z -axis of the IMU, represented by $\mathbf{z} = [0, 0, 1]^T$. The rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$ is defined as in Eqs. (82), (83), (84), and (85).

$$\mathbf{n}^i = \mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{g}_{\text{inv}}^i, \quad (82)$$

$$\alpha^i = \arccos \left(\frac{-z_g^i}{\sqrt{x_g^{i2} + y_g^{i2} + z_g^{i2}}} \right), \quad (83)$$

$$\mathbf{v}^i = \alpha^i \frac{\mathbf{n}^i}{\|\mathbf{n}^i\|}, \quad (84)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}} = f(\mathbf{v}^i), \quad (85)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}} \in \text{SO}(3)$ denotes the rotation matrix, and $\mathbf{v}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the rotation vector corresponding to the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$. The vector $\mathbf{n}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the rotation axis of the rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i , while $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes its rotation angle. The function $f(\cdot)$ refers to the Rodrigues' formula, which converts the rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i into the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$.

In the local coordinate system Σ_i , the coordinates of the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z are given by Eq. (86).

$$\mathbf{p}_{i_x}^i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}^i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}^i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (86)$$

The superscript i in $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}^i$ indicates that the coordinates are expressed in the local coordinate system Σ_i . As shown in Eq. (87), the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$ is employed to transform the coordinates of the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z from the local coordinate system Σ_i to the corrected local coordinate system Σ_i^{cor} .

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{p}_{i_x}^{\text{icor}} = (\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{p}_{i_y}^{\text{icor}} = (\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{p}_{i_z}^{\text{icor}} = (\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{cases}. \quad (87)$$

The superscript icor in $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}^{\text{icor}}$ indicates that the coordinate is expressed in the local coordinate frame Σ_i^{cor} . The rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}}$ represents the transformation from the local frame Σ_i to the local frame Σ_i^{cor} . Consequently, the transformation of the observed coordinates must employ the inverse rotation matrix $(\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}})^{-1}$. As shown in Eqs. (88) and (89), the pose transformation from node i to node j is denoted as $\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \text{SE}(3)$.

$$T_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{ij} & \mathbf{t}_{ij} \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \text{SE}(3), \mathbf{R}_{ij} \in \text{SO}(3), \quad (88)$$

$$\mathbf{t}_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ij} \\ y_{ij} \\ z_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^3. \quad (89)$$

The position of the virtual node j_x in the local coordinate system Σ_i is given by Eq. (90).

$$\mathbf{p}_{j_x}^i = \mathbf{R}_{ij} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{t}_{ij}. \quad (90)$$

The position of the virtual node j_x in the corrected local coordinate system Σ_i^{cor} is presented in Eq. (91).

$$\mathbf{p}_{j_x}^{\text{icor}} = (\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{cor}})^{-1} \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^i. \quad (91)$$

As shown in Eqs. (92), (93), and (94), the relative positions of the vectors $\overline{j_x i_x}$, $\overline{j_x i_y}$, and $\overline{j_x i_z}$ in the local coordinate system Σ_i^{cor} are provided.

$$\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor}} = \mathbf{p}_{i_x}^{\text{icor}} - \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^{\text{icor}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor}} \\ y_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor}} \\ z_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (92)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor}} = \mathbf{p}_{i_y}^{\text{icor}} - \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^{\text{icor}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor}} \\ y_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor}} \\ z_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (93)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor}} = \mathbf{p}_{i_z}^{\text{icor}} - \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^{\text{icor}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor}} \\ y_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor}} \\ z_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (94)$$

The projected coordinates of the vectors $\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor}}$, $\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor}}$, $\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor}}$ onto the horizontal plane are given by Eq. (95).

$$\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor}} \\ y_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor}} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor xy}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor}} \\ y_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor}} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor xy}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor}} \\ y_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (95)$$

Due to the complexity of the subscripts and superscripts used in these coordinates, their meanings are clarified as follows. In the coordinate $\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}}$, the subscripts j_x, i_x indicate that this is the coordinate of the vector $\overline{j_x i_x}$. The superscript icor denotes that the coordinate is expressed in the local coordinate frame Σ_i^{cor} . The superscript xy indicates that

the coordinate represents the projection onto the horizontal plane.

The parameters ω_{i_x, j_x, i_y} , ω_{i_x, j_x, i_z} , ω_{i_y, j_x, i_z} are subsequently computed. The lengths of the coordinates $\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}}$, $\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor xy}}$, $\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor xy}}$ are given by Eq. (96).

$$\rho_{i_x} = \|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}}\|, \rho_{i_y} = \|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor xy}}\|, \rho_{i_z} = \|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor xy}}\|. \quad (96)$$

The ratio of magnitudes is given by Eq. (97).

$$\rho_{i_x, j_x, i_y} = \frac{\rho_{i_y}}{\rho_{i_x}}, \rho_{i_x, j_x, i_z} = \frac{\rho_{i_z}}{\rho_{i_x}}, \rho_{i_y, j_x, i_z} = \frac{\rho_{i_z}}{\rho_{i_y}}. \quad (97)$$

The angle calculation is defined by Eq. (98).

$$\begin{cases} \theta_{i_x, j_x, i_y} = \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor xy}}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}}\| \|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor xy}}\|} \right) \\ \theta_{i_x, j_x, i_z} = \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor xy}}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_x}^{\text{icor xy}}\| \|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor xy}}\|} \right) \\ \theta_{i_y, j_x, i_z} = \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor xy}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor xy}}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_y}^{\text{icor xy}}\| \|\mathbf{p}_{j_x, i_z}^{\text{icor xy}}\|} \right) \end{cases}. \quad (98)$$

The parameters ω_{i_x, j_x, i_y} , ω_{i_x, j_x, i_z} , and ω_{i_y, j_x, i_z} are specified in Eq. (99).

$$\begin{cases} \omega_{i_x, j_x, i_y} = \rho_{i_x, j_x, i_y} e^{i\theta_{i_x, j_x, i_y}} \\ \omega_{i_x, j_x, i_z} = \rho_{i_x, j_x, i_z} e^{i\theta_{i_x, j_x, i_z}} \\ \omega_{i_y, j_x, i_z} = \rho_{i_y, j_x, i_z} e^{i\theta_{i_y, j_x, i_z}} \end{cases}. \quad (99)$$

The values of the parameters $z_{i_x, j_x}^{\text{cor}}$, $z_{i_y, j_x}^{\text{cor}}$, $z_{i_z, j_x}^{\text{cor}}$ are provided in Eqs. (92), (93), and (94), respectively. Utilizing the pose transformation from node i to node j , denoted as T_{ij} , along with the gravity direction at node i , expressed as $\mathbf{g}_{\text{ori}}^i = [x_g^i, y_g^i, z_g^i]^T$, the linear equation of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$ can be computed. The corresponding pseudocode is presented as Algorithm 2 in Supplementary Material S1.

A.2. Computation of parameters for the tetrahedra

$i_x - i_y - i_z - j_y$, $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_z$, and $i_x - i_y - i_z - i$

In the preceding section, the linear equations constructed from the three triangular faces of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_y$ (namely, triangles $\triangle j_y - i_x - i_y$, $\triangle j_y - i_x - i_z$, and $\triangle j_y - i_y - i_z$) were given by Eqs. (54) and (55).

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_y i_y} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_y i_z} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy} = \omega_{i_y j_y i_z} (p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_y}^{xy}) \end{cases} \quad (\text{same as (54)})$$

$$\begin{cases} z_{j_y} - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x j_y}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_y} - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y j_y}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_y} - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z j_y}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases} \quad (\text{same as (55)})$$

The variables $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}, p_{j_y}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ represent the projections of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, j_y , respectively, onto the horizontal plane, while $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_{j_y} \in \mathbb{R}$ denote the vertical coordinates of the corresponding nodes. The parameters $\omega_{i_x j_y i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_y i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_y i_z}, z_{i_x j_y}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_y}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_y}^{\text{cor}}$ were not explicitly defined in previous sections. The computational method for these parameters is presented below. Since the linear equation formulation for the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_y$ is analogous to that of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$, the same procedure described in Algorithm 2 can be applied. The only modification required is to replace the input condition “coordinates of virtual node j_x in local frame $\Sigma_j: \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^j = [1, 0, 0]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ ” with “coordinates of virtual node j_y in local frame $\Sigma_j: \mathbf{p}_{j_y}^j = [0, 1, 0]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ ”. Under this substitution, the output of the algorithm yields the parameters $\omega_{i_x j_y i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_y i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_y i_z}, z_{i_x j_y}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_y}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_y}^{\text{cor}}$.

In the preceding sections, the linear equations constructed from the three triangles of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_z$, namely triangle $\triangle j_z - i_x - i_y$, triangle $\triangle j_z - i_x - i_z$, and triangle $\triangle j_z - i_y - i_z$, were formulated as shown in Eqs. (56) and (57).

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_z i_y} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy} = \omega_{i_x j_z i_z} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy} = \omega_{i_y j_z i_z} (p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_{j_z}^{xy}) \end{cases} \quad (\text{same as (56)})$$

$$\begin{cases} z_{j_z} - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x j_z}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_z} - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y j_z}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_{j_z} - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z j_z}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases} \quad (\text{same as (57)})$$

The variables $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}, p_{j_z}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ denote the projections of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z and j_z onto the horizontal plane, respectively, while $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_{j_z} \in \mathbb{R}$ represent their corresponding vertical coordinates. The parameters $\omega_{i_x j_z i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_z i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_z i_z}, z_{i_x j_z}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_z}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_z}^{\text{cor}}$ have not been explicitly described in previous sections. The computation methods for these parameters are presented

below. Since the computation of the linear equation for the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_z$ is analogous to that for the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$, it suffices to modify the input condition in Algorithm 2 by replacing “coordinates of virtual node j_x in local frame $\Sigma_j: \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^j = [1, 0, 0]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ ” with “coordinates of virtual node j_z in local frame $\Sigma_j: \mathbf{p}_{j_z}^j = [0, 0, 1]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ ”. Under this modification, the output of the algorithm corresponds to the parameters $\omega_{i_x j_z i_y}, \omega_{i_x j_z i_z}, \omega_{i_y j_z i_z}, z_{i_x j_z}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y j_z}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z j_z}^{\text{cor}}$.

In the preceding sections, the linear equations constructed using the three triangular faces of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - i$ (namely, triangle $\triangle i - i_x - i_y$, triangle $\triangle i - i_x - i_z$, and triangle $\triangle i - i_y - i_z$) were presented in Eqs. (58) and (59).

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_i^{xy} = \omega_{i_x i i_y} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_i^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_i^{xy} = \omega_{i_x i i_z} (p_{i_x}^{xy} - p_i^{xy}) \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} - p_i^{xy} = \omega_{i_y i i_z} (p_{i_y}^{xy} - p_i^{xy}) \end{cases} \quad (\text{same as (58)})$$

$$\begin{cases} z_i - z_{i_x} = z_{i_x i}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_i - z_{i_y} = z_{i_y i}^{\text{cor}} \\ z_i - z_{i_z} = z_{i_z i}^{\text{cor}} \end{cases} \quad (\text{same as (59)})$$

The variables $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}, p_i^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ represent the projections of nodes i_x, i_y, i_z, i onto the horizontal plane, respectively; $z_{i_x}, z_{i_y}, z_{i_z}, z_i \in \mathbb{R}$ denote the vertical coordinates of the corresponding nodes. The parameters $\omega_{i_x i i_y}, \omega_{i_x i i_z}, \omega_{i_y i i_z}, z_{i_x i}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y i}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z i}^{\text{cor}}$ were not previously defined in terms of their computational methods in earlier sections. The computation of these parameters is detailed below. Since the linear equation for the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - i$ is analogous to that of the tetrahedron $i_x - i_y - i_z - j_x$, the method described in Algorithm 2 can be adapted. Specifically, the input condition “coordinates of virtual node j_x in local frame $\Sigma_j: \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^j = [1, 0, 0]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ ” is replaced by “coordinates of virtual node i in local frame $\Sigma_i: \mathbf{p}_i^i = [0, 0, 0]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ ”. Correspondingly, “the position of the virtual node j_x in the local coordinate system Σ_i is given by $\mathbf{p}_{j_x}^i = \mathbf{R}_{ij} \mathbf{p}_{j_x}^j + \mathbf{t}_{ij}$ ” is modified to “the position of the virtual node i in the local coordinate system Σ_i is given by $\mathbf{p}_i^i = [0, 0, 0]^T$ ”. Under this adaptation, the output parameters of the algorithm are “ $\omega_{i_x i i_y}, \omega_{i_x i i_z}, \omega_{i_y i i_z}, z_{i_x i}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_y i}^{\text{cor}}, z_{i_z i}^{\text{cor}}$ ”.

B. Pose transformation across different sensors

In this section, the process of converting data acquired from various types of sensors into pose transformations between different nodes is discussed. Pose transformations between two frames can be obtained using data from cameras,

LiDAR, IMU sensors, GPS sensors, wheel encoders, and loop closure detection. The pose transformations derived from each type of sensor are discussed in the following subsections.

B.1. Non-GPS sensors

The cases of camera and LiDAR sensors are first considered; these two types of sensors are capable of obtaining a deterministic relative pose transformation between two nodes (e.g., node i and node j), denoted as $T_{ij} \in SE(3)$. Typically, node i and node j correspond to two adjacent keyframes or two keyframes that are spatially very close.

Subsequently, for the IMU and wheel odometer sensors, the relative pose transformation obtained is generally between two consecutive keyframes, denoted as $T_{i-1,i} \in SE(3)$.

The loop closure module is also capable of estimating the relative pose transformation T_{ij} between two nodes (node i and node j). Typically, nodes i and j are adjacent nodes detected when the robot returns to a previously visited location after completing a loop. Although nodes i and j are temporally distant in the robot's trajectory, they are spatially proximal.

The pose transformation T_{ij} between nodes i and j , obtained through non-GPS sensors, can be converted into a set of linear equations defined between two sets of virtual nodes (virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z and virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z).

B.2. GPS sensors

GPS sensors exhibit distinctive characteristics in comparison to other types of sensors. The data obtained from GPS sensors consist of latitude and longitude values, which can be converted into metric distances using established formulas. Consequently, each position measurement from the GPS sensor corresponds to a fixed location in a global coordinate system defined by geographic coordinates. In contrast, other sensors, such as cameras and LiDAR, are only capable of measuring the relative pose transformation T_{ij} between two nodes, node i and node j . To derive the pose transformation between two distant nodes (e.g., node i and node $i+n$), it is necessary to incrementally compose the intermediate transformations, as given by $T_{i,i+n} = T_{i,i+1}T_{i+1,i+2} \cdots T_{i+n-1,i+n}$. This sequential composition introduces cumulative error in the estimated pose transformation $T_{i,i+n}$. In contrast, GPS sensors, owing to their operation in a fixed global coordinate frame, provide highly accurate estimates of the translational component $t_{i,i+n} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ even between spatially distant nodes (e.g., node i and node $i+n$). Therefore, GPS data play a critical role in maintaining the global consistency and structural accuracy of large-scale maps.

Another particular case of the GPS sensor is that the GPS data provides only translational information without any rotational data. Suppose the GPS data of node i (in the geodetic coordinate system) is obtained, followed by that of node j . In this case, only the translational displacement $t_{ij}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ from node i to node j in the geodetic coordinate system

can be determined, while rotational information remains unavailable. Consequently, the translational vector $t_{ij}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}$ obtained from the GPS sensor cannot be combined with the full pose transformation $T_{ij} \in SE(3)$ acquired from other sensors to construct linear equation constraints. Although it is possible to formulate nonlinear pose graph constraints, such an approach deviates from the objective of constructing an optimization algorithm based on linear equations.

The data obtained from GPS sensors typically include only latitude and longitude, without altitude information. Moreover, even when altitude data are available, their accuracy is significantly lower than that of the latitude and longitude measurements. When the GPS data consist solely of latitude and longitude, the planar translation between two nodes (nodes i and j) can be represented as $t_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^2$. In this case, a linear equation can be constructed using three nodes (nodes i , j , and k) based on a planar triangle, and the detailed procedure will be provided subsequently. If the GPS data include both latitude, longitude, and altitude, the translation between two nodes (nodes i and j) becomes a three-dimensional vector $t_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^3$. A linear equation can then be formulated using three nodes (nodes i , j , and k) based on a spatial triangle. However, this case is analogous to the planar triangle scenario, and the derivation follows a similar approach; therefore, the specific formulas are omitted here.

In the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, there are a total of n nodes (keyframes). Since the update frequency of GPS data is generally much lower than that of camera or IMU sensors, not every node is associated with corresponding GPS data. Let the set of indices of nodes with available GPS measurements be denoted by $\mathcal{G}_{\text{index}} = g(i), i \in [1, m]$. Each index $g(i)$ satisfies $g(i) \in [1, n]$, and the set contains m elements, corresponding to m GPS latitude and longitude measurements. The set of these m GPS measurements is defined as $\mathcal{G}_{\text{gps}} = \{pos_{g(i)} = [lon_{g(i)}, lat_{g(i)}]^T, g(i) \in [1, n], i \in [1, m]\}$. Let the i -th GPS coordinate be denoted as $pos_{g(i)} = [lon_{g(i)}, lat_{g(i)}]^T$, and the j -th GPS coordinate as $pos_{g(j)} = [lon_{g(j)}, lat_{g(j)}]^T$. As shown in Eq. (100), the relative translation vector between node i and node j can be obtained by converting their GPS coordinates using either the spherical distance formula or the UTM planar coordinate system.

$$t_{i,i+n} = f(pos_i, pos_{i+n}), \quad (100)$$

where the function $f(\cdot)$ transforms the geographic coordinates pos_i and pos_{i+n} of two nodes into a translation vector $t_{i,i+n} \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

Upon acquiring data from the GPS sensor, two types of linear equations are constructed: those based on adjacent GPS measurements and those based on non-adjacent (cross-node) GPS measurements. The following section first introduces the linear equations derived from adjacent GPS data.

Given that the i -th GPS data point is denoted as $pos_{g(i)}$, the $(i+1)$ -th as $pos_{g(i+1)}$, and the $(i+2)$ -th as $pos_{g(i+2)}$, the node $g(i+1)$ is employed as an intermediate node.

Accordingly, the relative position from node $g(i+1)$ to node $g(i)$ is defined as $\mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i)} = f(\text{pos}_{g(i+1)}, \text{pos}_{g(i)})$, and the relative position from node $g(i+1)$ to node $g(i+2)$ is given by $\mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i+2)} = f(\text{pos}_{g(i+1)}, \text{pos}_{g(i+2)})$. Furthermore, the relative position from node $g(i)$ to node $g(i+2)$ is expressed as $\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(i+2)} = f(\text{pos}_{g(i+2)}, \text{pos}_{g(i)})$. It is necessary to ensure that these three nodes are distinct, which can be verified using the criterion presented in Eq. (101).

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{g(i+1),g(i)} = \|\mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i)}\| > \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ \rho_{g(i+1),g(i+2)} = \|\mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i+2)}\| > \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ \rho_{g(i),g(i+2)} = \|\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(i+2)}\| > \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \end{cases} \quad (101)$$

After ensuring that there are no overlapping nodes, the linear equations represented by Eq. (102) and Eq. (103) can be constructed.

$$p_{g(i+2)}^{\text{xy}} - p_{g(i+1)}^{\text{xy}} = \omega_{i+1}(p_{g(i)}^{\text{xy}} - p_{g(i+1)}^{\text{xy}}), \quad (102)$$

$$\omega_{i+1} = \rho_{i+1} e^{i\theta_{i+1}}, \quad (103)$$

where $p_{g(i)} = x_{g(i)} + y_{g(i)}i$ denotes the complex coordinate of node $g(i)$ in the plane; $p_{g(i+1)} = x_{g(i+1)} + y_{g(i+1)}i$ represents the complex coordinate of node $g(i+1)$; and $p_{g(i+2)} = x_{g(i+2)} + y_{g(i+2)}i$ corresponds to the complex coordinate of node $g(i+2)$. The parameters ρ_{i+1} and θ_{i+1} are computed according to Eq. (104) and Eq. (105), respectively.

$$\rho_{i+1} = \frac{\rho_{g(i+1),g(i+2)}}{\rho_{g(i+1),g(i)}}, \quad (104)$$

$$\cos \theta_{i+1} = \frac{\mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i)} \cdot \mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i+2)}}{\|\mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i)}\| \|\mathbf{t}_{g(i+1),g(i+2)}\|}. \quad (105)$$

In addition, linear equations can be constructed across nodes using GPS data. Computing the translation vector $\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(i+1)}$ based on any two adjacent GPS measurements does not fully exploit the information provided by GPS. This is because the advantage of GPS data lies in its ability to maintain high accuracy in measuring relative positions even between spatially distant nodes. Therefore, in addition to constructing the aforementioned linear equations, it is necessary to formulate equations using GPS data from nodes that are far apart. To this end, three such nodes — $g(i)$, $g(j)$, and $g(k)$ — are selected from the GPS index set \mathcal{G}_{gps} , ensuring that these nodes are distinct, as indicated in Eq. (106).

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{g(i),g(j)} = \|\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(j)}\| > \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ \rho_{g(i),g(k)} = \|\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(k)}\| > \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \\ \rho_{g(j),g(k)} = \|\mathbf{t}_{g(j),g(k)}\| > \epsilon_{\text{thres}} \end{cases} \quad (106)$$

Moreover, the distances among these three nodes are approximately equal, or alternatively, they can be characterized by Eqs. (107), (108), and (109).

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\rho_{g(i),g(j)}}{\rho_{g(i),g(k)}} < p_{\text{thres}} & \text{if } \rho_{g(i),g(j)} \geq \rho_{g(i),g(k)} \\ \frac{\rho_{g(i),g(k)}}{\rho_{g(i),g(j)}} < p_{\text{thres}} & \text{if } \rho_{g(i),g(j)} < \rho_{g(i),g(k)} \end{cases}, \quad (107)$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\rho_{g(j),g(i)}}{\rho_{g(j),g(k)}} < p_{\text{thres}} & \text{if } \rho_{g(j),g(i)} \geq \rho_{g(j),g(k)} \\ \frac{\rho_{g(j),g(k)}}{\rho_{g(j),g(i)}} < p_{\text{thres}} & \text{if } \rho_{g(j),g(i)} < \rho_{g(j),g(k)} \end{cases}, \quad (108)$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\rho_{g(k),g(i)}}{\rho_{g(k),g(j)}} < p_{\text{thres}} & \text{if } \rho_{g(k),g(i)} \geq \rho_{g(k),g(j)} \\ \frac{\rho_{g(k),g(j)}}{\rho_{g(k),g(i)}} < p_{\text{thres}} & \text{if } \rho_{g(k),g(i)} < \rho_{g(k),g(j)} \end{cases}, \quad (109)$$

where p_{thres} denotes the ratio between the lengths of two sides. If the nodes $g(i)$, $g(j)$, $g(k)$ simultaneously satisfy the conditions specified in Eqs. (107), (108), and (109), it can be ensured that, within the triangle $\triangle g(i), g(j), g(k)$, the ratio of any two sides — defined as the length of the longer side divided by that of the shorter — is less than p_{thres} . The resulting triangle is approximately equilateral, which provides a uniform constraint on the position of each vertex of the triangle.

Since nodes $g(i)$, $g(j)$, and $g(k)$ are randomly selected across the entire map, the distances among these three points are generally large. Therefore, constructing a linear equation based on the similar triangle formed by these three nodes provides a strong constraint on the overall shape of the map. In order to preserve the geometric similarity of the triangle formed by $g(i)$, $g(j)$, and $g(k)$, relatively uniform and significant adjustments to their positions are required.

To identify as many such triangular combinations as possible within the GPS dataset \mathcal{G}_{gps} , the following approach is adopted. Three points are randomly selected from \mathcal{G}_{gps} and evaluated to determine whether they satisfy the specified edge ratio condition. If the condition is not met, the selection process is repeated. A maximum number of attempts, denoted as f_{max} , and a required number of triangles, denoted as Δ_{req} , can be predefined. Upon obtaining a valid set of three nodes $g(i)$, $g(j)$, $g(k)$ that meet the criteria, the corresponding linear equations can be constructed as shown in Eqs. (110) and (111).

$$p_{g(k)}^{\text{xy}} - p_{g(i)}^{\text{xy}} = \omega_{g(j),g(i),g(k)}(p_{g(j)}^{\text{xy}} - p_{g(i)}^{\text{xy}}), \quad (110)$$

$$\omega_{g(j),g(i),g(k)} = \rho_{g(j),g(i),g(k)} e^{i\theta_{g(j),g(i),g(k)}}. \quad (111)$$

Let $p_{g(i)} = x_{g(i)} + y_{g(i)}i$ denote the complex coordinate of node $g(i)$ in the plane; $p_{g(j)} = x_{g(j)} + y_{g(j)}i$ denote the complex coordinate of node $g(j)$; and $p_{g(k)} = x_{g(k)} + y_{g(k)}i$ denote the complex coordinate of node $g(k)$. The parameters $\rho_{g(j),g(i),g(k)}$ and $\theta_{g(j),g(i),g(k)}$ can be computed according to Eqs. (112) and (113), respectively.

$$\rho_{g(j),g(i),g(k)} = \frac{\rho_{g(i),g(k)}}{\rho_{g(i),g(j)}}, \quad (112)$$

$$\cos \theta_{g(j),g(i),g(k)} = \frac{\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(j)} \cdot \mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(k)}}{\|\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(j)}\| \|\mathbf{t}_{g(i),g(k)}\|}. \quad (113)$$

The linear equations derived from adjacent GPS data (Eq. (102)) and those derived from cross-node GPS data (Eq. (110)) are combined to form a system of equations, denoted as Eq. (64).

$$\mathbf{E}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = 0, \quad (\text{same as (64)})$$

where $\mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} \in \mathbb{C}^n$ represents the planar coordinate vector for all nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$. For the GPS data set \mathcal{G}_{gps} , two types of linear equations are constructed: one based on adjacent GPS data and the other on cross-node GPS data. The procedure for constructing linear equations from adjacent GPS data is detailed in Algorithm 3 in Supplementary Material S1.

The procedure for constructing the linear equations using cross-node GPS data is presented in Algorithm 4 in Supplementary Material S1.

C. Map Scale Estimation with GPS sensors

The coordinate vectors \mathbf{p}_v , \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} , and \mathbf{p}_v^z have been defined previously; however, for the sake of clarity, their definitions are briefly reiterated here. In the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, the set \mathcal{V} denotes all nodes (keyframes). Suppose there are n nodes in the set \mathcal{V} , and for each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$, three virtual nodes i_x , i_y , and i_z are defined in its local coordinate system Σ_i . The set of virtual nodes is given by $\mathcal{V}_v = \{i_x, i_y, i_z \mid i \in \mathcal{V}\}$. The coordinate vector of all virtual nodes is denoted as $\mathbf{p}_v = [p_{1_x}, p_{1_y}, p_{1_z}, \dots, p_{n_x}, p_{n_y}, p_{n_z}] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times n}$. The coordinate vector of the virtual nodes projected onto the plane is $\mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = [p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}}, \dots, p_{n_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{n_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{n_z}^{\text{xy}}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^n$, while the coordinate vector in the vertical direction is given by $\mathbf{p}_v^z = [z_{1_x}, z_{1_y}, z_{1_z}, \dots, z_{n_x}, z_{n_y}, z_{n_z}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Given the set of all pose transformations \mathbf{T}_{ij} as $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \mid i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$, each pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} between any pair of nodes (node i and node j) can be converted into 18 linear equations: 9 planar coordinate equations and 9 vertical coordinate equations. Accordingly, the complete system of linear equations corresponding to all pose transformations $\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}$ is formulated as follows (see Eqs. (65) and (66), as previously defined).

$$\mathbf{A}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_1. \quad (\text{same as (65)})$$

$$\mathbf{A}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z = \mathbf{b}^z + \mathbf{v}_2. \quad (\text{same as (66)})$$

Let the local coordinate frame of the first node, Σ_1 , be defined as the global coordinate frame Σ_g . Based on this definition, the coordinates of the remaining nodes can be subsequently computed. Alternatively, if another coordinate frame Σ_i is selected as the global frame Σ_g , the corresponding pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{1i} can be employed to transform all relevant coordinates into the coordinate system Σ_i . When Σ_1 is designated as the global coordinate frame Σ_g , the position of node 1 is given by $\mathbf{p}_1 = [0, 0, 0]^T$, the position of the virtual node 1_x is $\mathbf{p}_{1_x} = [1, 0, 0]^T$, the position of the virtual node 1_y is $\mathbf{p}_{1_y} = [0, 1, 0]^T$, and the position of the virtual node 1_z is $\mathbf{p}_{1_z} = [0, 0, 1]^T$.

In the vertical coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}_v^z \in \mathbb{R}^{3n}$, the vertical coordinate of the virtual node 1_x is given by $z_{1_x} = 0$, that of the virtual node 1_y is $z_{1_y} = 0$, and that of the virtual node 1_z is $z_{1_z} = 1$. According to the node localizability condition, once the full coordinates of a single node (e.g., node 1, and virtual nodes 1_x , 1_y , and 1_z) are determined, the coordinates of all other nodes can be computed. Moreover, since the linear equations in the vertical direction constrain only the relative vertical distances between nodes, there is no issue of scale ambiguity. Therefore, by substituting $z_{1_x}, z_{1_y}, z_{1_z}$ into the coordinate vector \mathbf{p}_v^z , the coordinates of the remaining nodes in \mathbf{p}_v^z can be computed using the linear equation $\mathbf{A}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z = \mathbf{b}^z$.

In the planar coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} \in \mathbb{C}^{3n}$, the planar coordinate of the virtual node 1_x is given by $p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}} = 1 + 0i$, that of the virtual node 1_y is $p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}} = 0 + 1i$, and the coordinate of the virtual node 1_z is $p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}} = 0 + 0i$. According to the node localizability condition, once the coordinates of a single node — including those of node 1, 1_x , 1_y , and 1_z — are determined, the coordinates of all other nodes can be computed. By substituting $p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}},$ and $p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}}$ into the coordinate vector \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} , the coordinates of the remaining nodes in \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} can be obtained by solving the linear equation $\mathbf{A}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}^{\text{xy}}$.

The linear system in the plane, $\mathbf{A}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}^{\text{xy}}$, geometrically implies that the shape of the projected configuration of all nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$ onto the plane is determined, whereas the scale remains undetermined and can be rescaled. This is because each linear equation corresponds to a constraint derived from similar triangles. If the coordinates of the other nodes in \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} are computed based on the three planar coordinates $p_{1_x}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_y}^{\text{xy}}, p_{1_z}^{\text{xy}}$, the scale of the entire planar configuration is essentially fixed by these three reference points. However, as this scale information propagates outward from node 1 to other nodes, the associated error tends to accumulate. For instance, even if the unit vectors along the three axes in the local coordinate system Σ_1 are set to have a unit norm (i.e., $\rho_{i,i_x} = 1, \rho_{i,i_y} = 1, \rho_{i,i_z} = 1$), the computed vectors in the local coordinate system Σ_n — formed by node n together

with nodes n_x , n_y , and n_z — may not preserve the unit norm (i.e., $\rho_{n,n_x}, \rho_{n,n_y}, \rho_{n,n_z}$ may deviate from 1). To address this issue and obtain a more accurate global scale of the map, the following method can be employed.

Let the planar coordinate of node 1 be defined as $p_1^{xy} = 0 + 0i$, while the planar coordinates of the virtual nodes are given by $p_{1_x}^{xy} = \rho + 0i$, $p_{1_y}^{xy} = 0 + \rho i$, $p_{1_z}^{xy} = 0 + 0i$, where ρ denotes the map scale to be estimated. The vertical coordinates of node 1 and its corresponding virtual nodes remain unchanged, i.e., $z_1 = 0$, $z_{1_x} = 0$, $z_{1_y} = 0$, $z_{1_z} = 1$; hence, the computation of the virtual node vector \mathbf{p}_v^z and the node vector \mathbf{p}^z is not affected. Let the planar coordinate vector of the virtual nodes $i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v \setminus \{1_x, 1_y, 1_z\}$ be denoted as $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{xy} = [p_{2_x}^{xy}, p_{2_y}^{xy}, p_{2_z}^{xy}, \dots, p_{n_x}^{xy}, p_{n_y}^{xy}, p_{n_z}^{xy}] \in \mathbb{C}^{3n-3}$. By substituting the planar coordinates $p_{1_x}^{xy}, p_{1_y}^{xy}, p_{1_z}^{xy}$ into the system, the linear equation $\mathbf{A}^{xy} \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} = \mathbf{b}^{xy} + \mathbf{v}_1$ is transformed into the form shown in Eq. (70).

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{xy} \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{xy} = \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^{xy} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}1}, \quad (\text{same as (70)})$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}1} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{sub}1})$ denotes the noise associated with each linear equation. The variance of each equation is represented by the variance σ_{ij}^2 of the corresponding pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} . The number of linear equations in the system remains unchanged, and the variance associated with each equation is not modified. Therefore, the error vector satisfies $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}1} = \mathbf{v}_1$, and the covariance matrix is given by $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{sub}1} = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_1$. The least-squares solution of the linear system is expressed as Eq. (71).

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{xy} = ((\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{xy})^T (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_1)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{xy})^{-1} (\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{xy})^T (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_1)^{-1} \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^{xy}. \quad (\text{same as (71)})$$

The planar coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{xy}$ represents the complex coordinates of the $3(n-1)$ virtual nodes from node 2 to node n . As shown in Eq. (114), each complex coordinate (e.g., $p_{i_x}^{xy}, p_{i_y}^{xy}, p_{i_z}^{xy}$) is a linear function of the unknown variable ρ in both its real and imaginary parts.

$$\begin{cases} p_{i_x}^{xy} = (a_{i_x} \rho + b_{i_x}) + (c_{i_x} \rho + d_{i_x})i \\ p_{i_y}^{xy} = (a_{i_y} \rho + b_{i_y}) + (c_{i_y} \rho + d_{i_y})i \\ p_{i_z}^{xy} = (a_{i_z} \rho + b_{i_z}) + (c_{i_z} \rho + d_{i_z})i \end{cases} \quad (114)$$

Simultaneously, the complex coordinates of the three virtual nodes $p_{1_x}^{xy}, p_{1_y}^{xy}, p_{1_z}^{xy}$ associated with node 1 are linear functions of the unknown variable ρ in both their real and imaginary parts. Consequently, for all virtual nodes $i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v$, the real and imaginary parts of their complex coordinates are also linear functions of the unknown variable ρ .

Given that the vertical coordinates of node 1, node 1_x , node 1_y , and node 1_z are $z_1 = 0$, $z_{1_x} = 0$, $z_{1_y} = 0$, and

$z_{1_z} = 1$, respectively, the planar coordinates of z_{1_x} , z_{1_y} , and z_{1_z} are substituted into the equation. As a result, the linear system $\mathbf{A}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z = \mathbf{b}^z + \mathbf{v}_2$ is transformed into Eq. (72).

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^z + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2}, \quad (\text{same as (72)})$$

where the coordinate vector is given by $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = [z_{2_x}, z_{2_y}, z_{2_z}, \dots, z_{n_x}, z_{n_y}, z_{n_z}] \in \mathbb{R}^{3n-3}$; $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{sub}2})$ denotes the noise associated with each linear equation. The number of linear equations in the system remains unchanged, and the variance corresponding to each equation is also preserved. Therefore, the error vector satisfies $\mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2} = \mathbf{v}_2$, and the covariance matrix satisfies $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{sub}2} = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_2$. The least squares solution of the linear system is given by Eq. (115).

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = ((\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z)^T (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_2)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z)^{-1} (\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z)^T (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_2)^{-1} \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^z. \quad (\text{same as (115)})$$

The vertical component of the virtual node coordinates, $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z \in \mathbb{R}^{3n-3}$, is a known quantity and does not contain the unknown variable ρ . The coordinate of node i can be represented using the coordinates of the three virtual nodes i_x, i_y , and i_z in the local coordinate system $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i$. Therefore, once the coordinates of all virtual nodes \mathbf{p}_v have been obtained, the coordinates of each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ can be computed using \mathbf{p}_v .

The coordinate vectors \mathbf{p} , \mathbf{p}^{xy} , \mathbf{p}^z have been defined previously; for the sake of clarity, their definitions are briefly revisited here. The coordinate vector for all nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$ is given by $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times n}$. The planar coordinate vector for all nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$ is denoted as $\mathbf{p}^{xy} = [p_{1_x}^{xy}, p_{1_y}^{xy}, \dots, p_{n_z}^{xy}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^n$, while the vertical coordinate vector is given by $\mathbf{p}^z = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The equations for computing the coordinates \mathbf{p}^{xy} and \mathbf{p}^z of all nodes $i \in \mathcal{V}$ using the virtual node coordinates \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} and \mathbf{p}_v^z are provided in Eqs. (67) and (68), as previously defined.

$$\mathbf{C}^{xy} \mathbf{p}^{xy} = \mathbf{D}^{xy} \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} + \mathbf{v}_3. \quad (\text{same as (67)})$$

$$\mathbf{C}^z \mathbf{p}^z = \mathbf{D}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z + \mathbf{v}_4. \quad (\text{same as (68)})$$

The least squares solutions to the two equations are given in Eqs. (115) and (116).

$$\mathbf{p}^{xy} = ((\mathbf{C}^{xy})^T \mathbf{C}^{xy})^{-1} (\mathbf{C}^{xy})^T \mathbf{D}^{xy} \mathbf{p}_v^{xy}, \quad (115)$$

$$\mathbf{p}^z = ((\mathbf{C}^z)^T \mathbf{C}^z)^{-1} (\mathbf{C}^z)^T \mathbf{D}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z. \quad (116)$$

As shown in Eq. (117), in the coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, each complex coordinate associated with node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ is

a linear function of the unknown variable ρ in both its real and imaginary parts.

$$p_i^{xy} = (a_i\rho + b_i) + (c_i\rho + d_i)i. \quad (117)$$

In the coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}^z \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the coordinates of each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ are deterministic values and do not contain the unknown variable ρ .

As shown in Eq. (118), the error function J_1 is defined accordingly. This error function represents the constraint that, in the local coordinate system Σ_i of each node i , the Euclidean distance from node i to the virtual node i_x should be 1, the distance from node i to node i_y should be 1, and the distance from node i to node i_z should also be 1.

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} (\|p_i - p_{i_x}\| - 1)^2 + (\|p_i - p_{i_y}\| - 1)^2 + (\|p_i - p_{i_z}\| - 1)^2 \\ &= A_1\rho^4 + B_1\rho^3 + C_1\rho^2 + D_1\rho + E_1 \end{aligned} \quad (118)$$

The error function J_2 is defined as shown in Eq. (119). If there exists a pose transformation $\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \text{SE}(3)$ between node i and node j , where the translational component is denoted by $\mathbf{t}_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, then the length between node i and node j is given by $\rho_{ij} = \|\mathbf{t}_{ij}\|$. Meanwhile, the magnitudes can also be computed using the estimated coordinates of node i , \mathbf{p}_i , and node j , \mathbf{p}_j , as a linear function of the unknown variable ρ . The error function is defined based on the discrepancy between these two magnitudes.

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &= \sum_{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}} (\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j\| - \rho_{ij})^2, \\ &= A_2\rho^4 + B_2\rho^3 + C_2\rho^2 + D_2\rho + E_2. \end{aligned} \quad (119)$$

As shown in Eq. (120), the error functions J_1 and J_2 are summed to obtain the overall error function J .

$$\begin{aligned} J &= J_1 + J_2 \\ &= A\rho^4 + B\rho^3 + C\rho^2 + D\rho + E \end{aligned} \quad (120)$$

In order to minimize the error function, the derivative of J is computed, as indicated in Eq. (122).

$$\frac{dJ}{d\rho} = 4A\rho^3 + 3B\rho^2 + 2C\rho + D = 0. \quad (121)$$

The three roots ρ_1, ρ_2, ρ_3 are calculated using the cubic equation formula. As illustrated in Eq. (122), after discarding the complex roots, the second derivative of J is employed to evaluate the remaining real root(s).

$$\frac{dJ^2}{d\rho^2} = 12A\rho^2 + 6B\rho + 2C. \quad (122)$$

If the second derivative at the root ρ_i is positive, then ρ_i corresponds to a local minimum of the function J , representing the desired map scale ρ . Conversely, if the second derivative at ρ_i is negative, then ρ_i corresponds to a local maximum of J . In cases where two values of ρ_i yield positive second derivatives, each ρ_i should be substituted into Eq. (120), and the one resulting in the smaller value of the function should be selected.

After obtaining the optimized map scale ρ , the coordinates $\mathbf{p}_v^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}^{3n}$ and $\mathbf{p}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}^n$ can be substituted accordingly. Utilizing the planar coordinate vector of the virtual nodes $\mathbf{p}_v^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}^{3n}$ along with the vertical coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}_v^z \in \mathbb{R}^{3n}$, the full coordinate vector of the virtual nodes $\mathbf{p}_v \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3n}$ can be constructed. Similarly, by combining the planar coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}^{xy} \in \mathbb{C}^n$ and the vertical coordinate vector $\mathbf{p}^z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for node $i \in \mathcal{V}$, the full coordinate vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times n}$ for the nodes can be obtained. The pseudocode for computing the map scale and node coordinates is presented in Algorithm 5 in Supplementary Material S1.

D. Outlier removal

In this paper, the linear equations are constructed based on the pose transformations \mathbf{T}_{ij} between nodes. If outliers exist in the set of pose transformations $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \mid i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$ within the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, the coefficients of the corresponding linear equations will also be affected by these outliers. When solving the linear system using the least squares method, each equation corresponds to an individual error term. The presence of outliers can lead to significant deviations in the solution of the system.

In nonlinear optimization-based SLAM approaches, each pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} is associated with an observation function to construct an error function $h(\mathbf{T}_{ij})$. Subsequently, the corresponding error term is defined as $e(\mathbf{T}_{ij}) = h(\mathbf{T}_{ij})^2$. The overall cost function J is then obtained by summing all individual error terms. As shown in Eq. (123), a robust kernel function is typically applied to each error term to mitigate the influence of outliers.

$$\rho(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}x^2 & \text{if } |x| \leq \sigma \\ \sigma(|x| - \frac{1}{2}\sigma) & \text{if } |x| > \sigma \end{cases}. \quad (123)$$

The robust function $\rho(\cdot)$ increases rapidly near zero, while its growth slows significantly beyond a certain range. With the introduction of the robust function, the error function J is modified as shown in Eq. (124).

$$J = \sum_{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}} \rho(h(\mathbf{T}_{ij})^2). \quad (124)$$

Due to the presence of a robust cost function, even when a given pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} is an outlier, the corresponding error term does not attain a large numerical value. Consequently, the influence of outliers on the overall error

function remains limited. Moreover, the original error term $e(\mathbf{T}_{ij}) = h(\mathbf{T}_{ij})^2$ is a nonlinear function, and the modified error term with the robust function, $\rho(h(\mathbf{T}_{ij})^2)$, also remains nonlinear. Therefore, numerical optimization methods are still employed to minimize the error function.

However, the linear equations in this paper do not permit the application of robust functions. If a robust function is applied outside each residual term formed by the linear equations, the resulting formulation becomes nonlinear. The primary purpose of constructing the pose transformation as a linear equation is to reduce computational complexity. Employing a nonlinear formulation would therefore negate this objective.

Reference Wu (2025) proposed a method for outlier removal in pose transformations. As the procedure involves multiple steps, only the core principles are briefly summarized here. The algorithm takes as input the complete set of pose transformations in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, where $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \mid i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$, and produces as output a refined set of pose transformations $\mathcal{E}' = \{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \mid i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$ with outliers removed. By constructing linear equations using only the transformations in \mathcal{E}' , the influence of outliers on the system of equations can be effectively mitigated.

The algorithm requires assigning a prior outlier probability p_{ij} to each pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} in the input set of pose transformations $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathbf{T}_{ij} \mid i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$. This probability does not need to be precisely accurate; it can be approximately estimated using the variance σ_{ij}^2 associated with the pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} . For instance, p_{ij} can be determined using the approach described in Eq. (125).

$$p_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0.1, & \text{if } \sigma_{ij}^2 < \sigma_{\text{thres1}}^2 \\ 0.2, & \text{if } \sigma_{\text{thres1}}^2 \leq \sigma_{ij}^2 < \sigma_{\text{thres2}}^2 \\ 0.3, & \text{if } \sigma_{\text{thres2}}^2 \leq \sigma_{ij}^2 \end{cases}. \quad (125)$$

The proposed outlier removal algorithm employs the probability p_{ij} to identify potential paths between different nodes, specifically node i and node j , where the pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{ij} represents the edge along the path. Accordingly, the algorithm attempts to determine a path composed predominantly of edges with fewer outliers to achieve the transformation from node i to node j .

The general procedure of the outlier removal algorithm is as follows. Given a graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, assume there exist two nodes $p_1, p_2 \in \mathcal{V}$. As illustrated in Fig. 11, three pose transformation matrices $\mathbf{T}_{12}^1, \mathbf{T}_{12}^2, \mathbf{T}_{12}^3$ are defined between nodes p_1 and p_2 .

As shown in Fig. 12, the transformation between nodes p_1 and p_2 can also be established via alternative intermediary nodes, such as p_3, p_4 , or p_5 . Under such conditions, the pose transformation from p_1 to p_2 is given by Eq. (126).

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{T}_{12}^4 = \mathbf{T}_{13}\mathbf{T}_{32} \\ \mathbf{T}_{12}^5 = \mathbf{T}_{14}\mathbf{T}_{42} \\ \mathbf{T}_{12}^6 = \mathbf{T}_{15}\mathbf{T}_{52} \end{cases}. \quad (126)$$

As shown in Fig. 13, nodes p_1 and p_2 can be connected via two intermediate nodes, such as (p_6, p_7) , (p_8, p_9) , or (p_{10}, p_{11}) . The corresponding pose transformation from p_1 to p_2 is then computed as shown in Eq. (127).

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{T}_{12}^7 = \mathbf{T}_{16}\mathbf{T}_{67}\mathbf{T}_{72} \\ \mathbf{T}_{12}^8 = \mathbf{T}_{18}\mathbf{T}_{89}\mathbf{T}_{92} \\ \mathbf{T}_{12}^9 = \mathbf{T}_{1,10}\mathbf{T}_{10,11}\mathbf{T}_{11,2} \end{cases}. \quad (127)$$

As a result, a total of nine pose transformations from node 1 to node 2 are obtained, denoted as \mathbf{T}_{12}^i , where $i \in [1, 9]$. If all transformations used — represented by the set \mathcal{E} — are free from outliers, the transformations \mathbf{T}_{12}^i are expected to be highly consistent. In contrast, if any transformation is an outlier, the corresponding \mathbf{T}_{12}^i will exhibit a significant deviation from the others. To address this, each transformation \mathbf{T}_{12}^i is decomposed into its translation and rotation vector components, and statistical outlier removal is then performed on each component using the Interquartile Range (IQR) method.

E. Estimation of local coordinate systems

In the SLAM problem, it is necessary to estimate the pose of each node, which includes both the translation and rotation of each node in the global coordinate system. In the preceding section, the translation values for all nodes have been computed. Based on this, the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i , which represents the orientation of the local coordinate system Σ_i with respect to the global coordinate system Σ_g , can be determined. This is achieved by analyzing the discrepancies between the global coordinates and the observed coordinates of neighboring nodes $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ for each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$, using a point cloud registration algorithm. The specific procedure for computing the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i is outlined below.

The global coordinates of each node in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ have been computed as $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times n}$ within the global coordinate system Σ_g . Let the global coordinate of node i be denoted by $p_i = [x_i, y_i, z_i]^T$. For a neighboring node $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$, its global coordinate is given by $p_j = [x_j, y_j, z_j]^T$. The relative coordinate of node j with respect to node i is thus defined as $p_j^r = [x_j - x_i, y_j - y_i, z_j - z_i]^T$. The collection of relative coordinates of all neighboring nodes of node i in the global coordinate system is represented by the matrix $\mathbf{P}_i^n = [p_{j_1}^r, \dots, p_{j_n}^r] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times |\mathcal{N}_i|}$, $j_1, \dots, j_n \in \mathcal{N}_i$.

Subsequently, the pose transformation from node i to its neighboring node $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ is defined as $\mathbf{T}_{ij} = [\mathbf{R}_{ij}, \mathbf{t}_{ij}; 1, 0] \in SE(3)$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$, where the translation vector is given by $\mathbf{t}_{ij} = [x_{ij}, y_{ij}, z_{ij}]^T$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$. Accordingly, the relative position vectors of the neighboring nodes $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ in the local coordinate system Σ_i are denoted as $\mathbf{Q}_i^n = [\mathbf{t}_{i,j_1}, \dots, \mathbf{t}_{i,j_n}] = [\mathbf{q}_{i,j_1}, \dots, \mathbf{q}_{i,j_n}] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times |\mathcal{N}_i|}$, $j_1, \dots, j_n \in \mathcal{N}_i$.

The global coordinates of the virtual nodes $i_x, i_y, i_z \in \mathcal{V}_v$ corresponding to each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ have been computed in the global coordinate frame Σ_g , and are denoted as $\mathbf{p}_{i_x} = [x_{i_x}, y_{i_x}, z_{i_x}]^T$, $\mathbf{p}_{i_y} = [x_{i_y}, y_{i_y}, z_{i_y}]^T$, and $\mathbf{p}_{i_z} =$

$[x_{i_z}, y_{i_z}, z_{i_z}]^T$, respectively. The global coordinate of node i is given by $\mathbf{p}_i = [x_i, y_i, z_i]^T$. Accordingly, the coordinates of the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z relative to node i are expressed as in Eq. (128).

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{p}_{i_x}^r = [x_{i_x} - x_i, y_{i_x} - y_i, z_{i_x} - z_i]^T \\ \mathbf{p}_{i_y}^r = [x_{i_y} - x_i, y_{i_y} - y_i, z_{i_y} - z_i]^T \\ \mathbf{p}_{i_z}^r = [x_{i_z} - x_i, y_{i_z} - y_i, z_{i_z} - z_i]^T \end{cases}. \quad (128)$$

The relative position vectors of the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in the global coordinate system are denoted as $\mathbf{P}_i^v = [\mathbf{p}_{i_x}^r, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}^r, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}^r] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$. The coordinates of the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in the local coordinate system Σ_i are given by $\mathbf{p}_{i_x}^i = [1, 0, 0]^T$, $\mathbf{p}_{i_y}^i = [0, 1, 0]^T$, and $\mathbf{p}_{i_z}^i = [0, 0, 1]^T$, respectively. Accordingly, the coordinate matrix of the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z in the local coordinate system Σ_i is represented as $\mathbf{Q}_i^v = [\mathbf{p}_{i_x}^i, \mathbf{p}_{i_y}^i, \mathbf{p}_{i_z}^i] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$.

The coordinate vectors \mathbf{P}_i^n and \mathbf{P}_i^v are concatenated to form $\mathbf{P}_i = [\mathbf{P}_i^n, \mathbf{P}_i^v] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times (|\mathcal{N}_i|+1)}$. Similarly, \mathbf{Q}_i^n and \mathbf{Q}_i^v are combined to obtain $\mathbf{Q}_i = [\mathbf{Q}_i^n, \mathbf{Q}_i^v] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times (|\mathcal{N}_i|+1)}$. Subsequently, the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i of the local coordinate system at node i can be computed using a point set registration method.

The coordinate vectors \mathbf{P}_i and \mathbf{Q}_i were constructed using the neighboring nodes $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ of node i and the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z . Although it is also possible to include the virtual coordinates j_x, j_y, j_z of the neighboring nodes $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ in the coordinate vectors, this was not adopted in the current setting for the following reasons. First, the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i can be obtained as long as three reference points are available, such as the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z . Second, since both the neighboring nodes $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ and the virtual nodes i_x, i_y, i_z have already been utilized, incorporating the virtual nodes j_x, j_y, j_z for each j may unnecessarily increase the computational complexity.

Given a set of points with position vectors in the global coordinate frame Σ_g , denoted as $\mathbf{P}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times (|\mathcal{N}_i|+1)}$, and their corresponding position vectors in the local coordinate frame Σ_i , denoted as $\mathbf{Q}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times (|\mathcal{N}_i|+1)}$, the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_i is employed to construct the error function as defined in Eq. (129).

$$E(\mathbf{R}_i) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \|\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{p}_{ij}^r - \mathbf{q}_{ij}\|^2. \quad (129)$$

The objective is to determine the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_i \in \text{SO}(3)$ that minimizes the error function $E(\mathbf{R}_i)$. This problem falls within the scope of point cloud registration and can be addressed using the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) method of the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm to compute the matrix \mathbf{R}_i . The matrix \mathbf{R}_i represents the rotation that transforms a point set from the global coordinate system Σ_g to the local coordinate system Σ_i . Since the

rotation of the coordinate system is opposite to the rotation of the point set, the rotation matrix of the local coordinate system Σ_i with respect to the global coordinate system Σ_g is given by $(\mathbf{R}_i)^{-1}$. According to the SVD-based approach in the ICP algorithm, the rotation matrix that minimizes the error function $E(\mathbf{R}_i)$ is obtained as shown in Eq. (131).

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H} &= \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{Q}_i^T, \\ &= \mathbf{U} \Sigma \mathbf{V}^T. \end{aligned} \quad (130)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{U}^T. \quad (131)$$

The SVD is performed on the matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ to obtain the orthogonal matrices \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} . The rotation matrix is then computed as $\mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{U}^T$. However, if the point sets \mathbf{P}_i or \mathbf{Q}_i are degenerate, the resulting matrix \mathbf{R}_i may correspond to a reflection, indicated by $\det(\mathbf{R}_i) = -1$. In such cases, the reflection matrix \mathbf{R}_i can be corrected to a proper rotation matrix using Eq. (132).

$$\mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{V} \text{diag}([1, 1, -1]) \mathbf{U}^T. \quad (132)$$

The complete formulation for computing the rotation matrix is provided in Eq. (133).

$$\mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{V} \text{diag}([1, 1, |\mathbf{V} \mathbf{U}^T|]) \mathbf{U}^T. \quad (133)$$

The inverse rotation matrix $(\mathbf{R}_i)^{-1}$ can be computed for each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ of the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$; the corresponding algorithm is presented as pseudocode in Algorithm 7 in Supplementary Material S1.

F. Linear equation computation methods

In the absence of the GPS sensor, the linear equations to be computed are given by Eqs. (67), (68), (70), and (72).

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}1}, \quad (\text{same as (70)})$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^z + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2}, \quad (\text{same as (72)})$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{D}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_v^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_3, \quad (\text{same as (67)})$$

$$\mathbf{C}^z \mathbf{p}^z = \mathbf{D}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z + \mathbf{v}_4. \quad (\text{same as (68)})$$

When the GPS sensor is utilized, the linear equations to be computed are presented in Eqs. (67), (72), and (75).

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub,acc}}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{G}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}6}, \quad (\text{same as (75)})$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z \mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z = \mathbf{b}_{\text{sub}}^z + \mathbf{v}_{\text{sub}2}, \quad (\text{same as (72)})$$

$$\mathbf{C}^z \mathbf{p}^z = \mathbf{D}^z \mathbf{p}_v^z + \mathbf{v}_4. \quad (\text{same as (68)})$$

Let the number of nodes be denoted by n . Each node is associated with a virtual coordinate system comprising four nodes (e.g., node i , i_x , i_y , and i_z). Accordingly, the total number of nodes involved in the computation of the linear system is $4n$. The coordinate system of node 1 (i.e., nodes 1, 1_x , 1_y , and 1_z) is assumed to be known and is used to fix the position of the global coordinate system. Consequently, the vector $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ is a complex-valued vector of dimension $3(n-1)$, and the vector $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z$ is a real-valued vector of dimension $3(n-1)$. The vector \mathbf{p}^{xy} is a complex-valued vector of dimension n , while the vector \mathbf{p}^z is a real-valued vector of dimension n .

Let the number of pose constraints be denoted by m . Each pose constraint (e.g., T_{ij}) is converted into 9 complex linear equations (Eq.(70)), 9 real linear equations (Eq.(72)), 3 complex linear equations (Eq.(67)), and 3 real linear equations (Eq.(68)). The matrix dimensions corresponding to the linear equations are first analyzed for the case without the use of GPS sensors. Specifically, the matrix $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ is a complex matrix of dimension $9m \times 3(n-1)$, and the matrix $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z$ is a real matrix of the same dimension, i.e., $9m \times 3(n-1)$. The matrix $\mathbf{D}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ is a complex matrix of dimension $(n-1) \times 3(n-1)$, while $\mathbf{D}_{\text{sub}}^z$ is a real matrix of the same size. Since the number of pose constraints m is typically much greater than the number of nodes n , the matrices $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ and $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z$ are generally tall matrices, with significantly more rows than columns. The matrix dimensions corresponding to the linear equations in the case where GPS sensors are used can be analyzed in a similar manner. In the following, the discussion is limited to the case without GPS sensors.

The specific algorithms and libraries for solving linear equations are discussed below. Initially, the unknowns $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ and $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sub}}^z$ in Eqs. (70) and (72) are computed using the least squares method, for example, by employing the `pinv` function from the NumPy library. This function utilizes SVD to solve linear systems, and is suitable for small-scale overdetermined systems. However, its computational speed is relatively slow. This is primarily due to the fact that the matrices $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ and $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z$ have significantly more rows than columns, resulting in high computational cost during the SVD process.

Subsequently, iterative algorithms such as LMSR and LSQR can be employed to directly solve the linear systems represented by Eqs. (70) and (72). In practice, functions such as the `lsqr` function from the SciPy library can be utilized for this purpose. However, even in this case, it is still necessary to process the matrices $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ and $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z$. Empirical measurements indicate that the computational speed remains relatively slow.

The sparse Cholesky decomposition from the `scipy.sparse` library and the conjugate gradient method from the `pyamg`

library will be employed to solve the linear system. As both libraries do not support computations involving complex matrices, the complex linear system in Eq. (70) is reformulated as an equivalent real-valued system using the following procedure. Consider a complex linear system given by $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$, where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{C}^m$. Let $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}_r + i\mathbf{A}_i$, where \mathbf{A}_r and \mathbf{A}_i denote the real and imaginary parts of \mathbf{A} , respectively. Similarly, define $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_r + \mathbf{x}_i i$ and $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{b}_r + \mathbf{b}_i i$. The original complex equation $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$ can then be transformed into the real-valued system represented by Eqs. (134), (135), and (136).

$$(\mathbf{A}_r + \mathbf{A}_i i)(\mathbf{x}_r + \mathbf{x}_i i) = \mathbf{b}_r + \mathbf{b}_i i, \quad (134)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_r \mathbf{x}_r - \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{b}_r, \quad (135)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{x}_r + \mathbf{A}_r \mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{b}_i. \quad (136)$$

Let the new real-valued variable be defined as $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{x}_r^T, \mathbf{x}_i^T]^T$. Accordingly, the complex linear equation in Eq.(136) is transformed into the real-valued linear equations given in Eqs.(137) and (138).

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_r & -\mathbf{A}_i \\ \mathbf{A}_i & \mathbf{A}_r \end{bmatrix}, \tilde{\mathbf{b}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_r \\ \mathbf{b}_i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (137)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{x}} = \tilde{\mathbf{b}}, \quad (138)$$

where the matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ has dimensions $\mathbb{R}^{2m \times 2n}$, the vector $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ has dimensions \mathbb{R}^{2n} , and the vector $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ has dimensions \mathbb{R}^{2m} . Following the same approach, the complex linear equation in Eq.(70) is transformed into the real-valued linear equation presented in Eq.(139).

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} = \hat{\mathbf{b}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} + \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\text{sub}1}. \quad (139)$$

The matrix $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ has dimensions of $18m \times 6(n-1)$, where n denotes the number of nodes and m represents the number of pose constraints. The vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ has dimensions of $6(n-1)$, while the vector $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ has dimensions of $18m$. Although Eq. (67) is also a complex linear equation, it is used to compute \mathbf{p}^{xy} given \mathbf{p}_v^{xy} . The matrix \mathbf{C}^{xy} is a quasi-diagonal matrix, and the associated computational cost is minimal. Therefore, no transformation is applied to the linear equation in Eq. (67).

To compute the least-squares solution of Eq. (139), Eqs. (140) and (141) are defined accordingly.

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{H}_1 = (\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_1^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} \\ \mathbf{b}_1 = (\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_1^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} \end{cases}, \quad (140)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_1 \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}} = \mathbf{b}_1. \quad (141)$$

To compute the least-squares solution of Eq. (72), Eqs. (142) and (143) are defined accordingly.

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{H}_2 = (\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^z)^T \Sigma_1^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^z \\ \mathbf{b}_2 = (\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^z)^T \Sigma_1^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_{\text{sub}}^z \end{cases}, \quad (142)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_2 \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{sub}}^z = \mathbf{b}_2. \quad (143)$$

The matrix \mathbf{H}_1 has dimensions of $6(n-1) \times 6(n-1)$, and the matrix \mathbf{H}_2 has dimensions of $3(n-1) \times 3(n-1)$. The dimensions of these matrices are solely determined by the number of nodes, and are significantly smaller than the number of pose constraints m . Given that the matrices $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\text{sub}}^z$ are full-rank, it follows that both \mathbf{H}_1 and \mathbf{H}_2 are symmetric positive definite matrices. Furthermore, due to the distribution characteristics of the pose constraints in graph G , \mathbf{H}_1 and \mathbf{H}_2 may exhibit partially sparse structures. Therefore, the sparse Cholesky decomposition method is employed to solve the linear systems in Eqs. (141) and (143). Specifically, functions such as the `cholesky` function from the `scipy.sparse` library are utilized. Many sparse Cholesky decomposition libraries exploit the sparsity patterns of matrices through various optimization techniques, including variable reordering strategies such as Approximate Minimum Degree (AMD), Column AMD (COLAMD), and Nested Dissection. Empirical measurements indicate that this method achieves high computational efficiency when the matrix dimensions are relatively small.

Furthermore, for the linear equations represented by Eq.(141) and Eq.(143), the Conjugate Gradient (CG) method can also be employed for their solution due to the fact that the matrices \mathbf{H}_1 and \mathbf{H}_2 are symmetric positive-definite. The CG method is an iterative approach for solving linear systems, and its accuracy depends on the specified termination criteria. In practice, various function libraries, such as the `pyamg` library, provide implementations of the CG method optimized for sparse matrices. These implementations incorporate several enhancement techniques, including the Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient (PCG) method, Jacobi (diagonal) preconditioning, Incomplete Cholesky factorization, and Multigrid methods. Empirical evaluations indicate that when the dimensions of matrices \mathbf{H}_1 and \mathbf{H}_2 are relatively small, the computational efficiency of the CG method is generally inferior to that of sparse Cholesky decomposition. However, as the matrix dimension increases (e.g., when the number of nodes exceeds 1000), the performance of the CG method becomes comparable to or even surpasses that of sparse Cholesky decomposition. In summary, sparse Cholesky decomposition is recommended for solving linear systems when the matrix dimension is relatively low (e.g., fewer than 1000 nodes). In contrast, for higher-dimensional

matrices, the Conjugate Gradient method is a more suitable choice.

G. Local optimization versus global optimization

In practical SLAM systems, local optimization is typically employed, wherein only the poses of the current node and a subset of historical nodes are optimized. Once a sufficient number of nodes have been accumulated, global optimization is subsequently performed. Various strategies for local optimization have been proposed, such as the sliding window approach or the use of multiple submaps. The algorithm proposed in this paper is also compatible with local optimization strategies, including the sliding window method. In this approach, linear equations are constructed using the nodes within the sliding window, while the remaining nodes are treated as fixed, using the previously optimized values.

When employing the sliding window method for local optimization, the storage of matrices $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^{\text{xy}}$ and $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sub}}^z$ must be optimized accordingly in the implementation. This is because the coefficient matrices of the linear equations within the window must be dynamically assembled into a temporary optimization matrix $\mathbf{A}_{\text{slide}}$. Subsequently, for nodes that fall outside the sliding window, their corresponding values are treated as fixed and are used to compute the right-hand side vector $\mathbf{b}_{\text{slide}}$ of the linear system. It is therefore unnecessary to recompute $\mathbf{b}_{\text{slide}}$ from all nodes at each iteration; instead, incremental computation is adopted.

In our algorithm, it is necessary to apply an outlier rejection method to each pose transformation to determine whether it constitutes an outlier. This step can be implemented during local optimization, and the resulting classification can generally be reused during global optimization, rather than re-evaluating all transformations for outlier status.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zhitao Wu: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft. **Guangyu Liu:** Resources, Supervision, Writing – review and editing.

References

- Bai, F., Vidal-Calleja, T., Grisetti, G., 2021. Sparse pose graph optimization in cycle space. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* 37, 1381 – 1400.
- Bailey, T., Nieto, J., Guivant, J., Stevens, M., Nebot, E., 2006. Consistency of the EKF-SLAM algorithm, in: 2006 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems, pp. 3562 – 3568.
- Briales, J., Gonzalez-Jimenez, J., 2016. Fast global optimality verification in 3D SLAM, in: 2016 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), pp. 4630 – 4636.
- Carlone, L., Calafiore, G.C., Tommolillo, C., Dellaert, F., 2016. Planar pose graph optimization: Duality, optimal solutions, and verification. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* 32, 545 – 565.
- Cheng, J., Jiang, Z., Zhang, Y., Kim, J., 2014. Toward robust linear SLAM, in: 2014 IEEE International Conference on Mechatronics and Automation, pp. 705 – 710.

Figure 2: The position of nodes i, j, k

Figure 5: The coordinate system of node i and node j

Figure 3: The position of point i, j, k and its projection point on the plane

Figure 6: Precisely estimated trajectory

Figure 4: The position of nodes i, j, k, l

Figure 7: Coarsely estimated trajectory

Figure 8: APE values for selected algorithms

Figure 9: RPE values for selected algorithms

Figure 10: Computation time for different algorithms

Figure 13: Measurement utilizing two intermediate node2

Figure 11: Measurement without utilizing central node

Figure 12: Measurement utilizing one intermediate node